

D5.5 Report on assessment of low-tech analytical techniques for the evaluation conservation treatments

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GLOSSARY

AR	Augmented Reality
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DES	Deep Eutectic Solvent
DMC	Dimethyl Carbonate
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
FHM	Full width at Half Maximum
FT-LSI	Fourier Transform - Laser Speckle Imaging
GA	Grant Agreement
GVL	Gamma-Valerolactone
H2020	Horizon 2020
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LED	Light Emitting Diode
LSI	Laser Speckle Imaging
OB	Operational Board
OM	Optical Microscopy
OO	Outreach Officer
PA 6,6	Polyamide 6,6
PHB	Project Handbook
PM	Project Manager
PC	Project Coordinator
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PO	Project Officer (European Commission)

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RMQAP	Risk Management & Quality Assurance Plan
ROI	Region of Interest
RTI	Reflectance Transformation Imaging
SCC	Stress Corrosion Cracking
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SP	Pure silver
SS	Sterling silver
UV	Ultraviolet
UvA	University of Amsterdam
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive summary

This deliverable aims to assess and improve the accessibility of low-tech analytical techniques for application in the field of conservation. Low-tech techniques are defined as simple, cost-effective, low-energy, and easy-to-use methods that require minimal equipment or specialized expertise. Most conservators already have access to low-tech methods and simple approaches in the field, such as assessing the effectiveness of cleaning treatments using Ultraviolet (UV) light. Rather than viewing these practices as outdated, this initiative seeks to reevaluate their effectiveness under specific conditions and acknowledge both their limitations and potential benefits. Low-tech methods provide socio-economic sustainability benefits that enhance the global sustainability of conservation efforts, while upholding high professional standards. The selection and protocol development of these low-tech techniques carefully considered their environmental impact, with a focus on material choice, energy consumption, digital sobriety, economic accessibility, and alignment with circular economy principles.

Five potential projects were initially identified based on the needs of the conservation field and their sustainability. These projects were further refined for feasibility through a literature review and the expertise within the consortium. Ultimately, three promising projects were selected:

Project 1: Protocol for assessing the cleaning of paintings under ultraviolet illumination.

Project 2: Protocol for cleaning assessment of metal surfaces, specifically silver.

Project 5: Evaluation of cleaning and consolidation treatments using Laser Speckle Imaging (LSI).

The findings from the three projects underscore the advantages and limitations of various diagnostic techniques in art conservation:

Project 1 showed that while monochromatic filters have limited practical advantages in assessing UV-induced photoluminescence in varnishes, they can enhance visibility in specific conditions, potentially revealing otherwise hidden details. However, their usefulness is limited by reduced photoluminescence intensity and their effectiveness only in dark environments.

Project 2 highlighted the value of Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) for revealing surface details missed by traditional photography. RTI proved particularly useful in assessing the impact of cleaning on metals like silver and copper, detecting potential etching of base metals during cleaning. However, additional imaging techniques are necessary for comprehensive analysis.

Project 5 demonstrated the potential of Fourier Transform Laser Speckle Imaging (FT-LSI) for monitoring solvent spread and retention in paintings, offering critical insights for optimizing varnish removal methods. FT-LSI shows promise for evaluating solvent dynamics in real-world conservation, though the effect of paint color on results suggests further research is needed.

Key factors for green evaluation included accessibility or ease of construction (Projects 1, 2, and 5), low energy consumption (Project 1), sample reuse (Projects 1 and 5), development with green protocols (Project 2), and a focus on digital sobriety (Projects 1,2 and 5). Collectively, these projects emphasize the importance of continued development and application of low-tech techniques to enhance conservation practices and support the sustainable preservation of cultural heritage.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to assess and enhance the accessibility of low-tech analytical techniques for application in the field of conservation. Low-tech analytical techniques defined as are simple, cost-effective, low energy consumption and easy-to-use methods that require minimal equipment or specialized knowledge. Most conservators have access to low-tech techniques and very simple approaches in the field to assess conservation treatments, like the effectiveness of cleaning with UV light. Rather than considering these practices as obsolete, we will reevaluate their effectiveness in specific conditions and acknowledge their limitations and opportunities. This involves aligning these basic tests with a profound grasp of the underlying system mechanics, along with advanced techniques like photoluminescence and X-ray tomographic imaging developed and applied in WP5. There is more to gain in properly evaluating low-tech tests in real-world situations and understanding more clearly when they are effective and when they are not. This builds knowledge and helps conservators decide when advanced methods might be better if basic tests have limitations. This approach will promote the sustainable and efficient utilization of resources while enhancing the dissemination of knowledge.

The selection of the topics took place by discussion by all partners from task 5.4. Five potential projects were identified based on the needs of the conservation field, their sustainability and further refined for feasibility through a review of relevant literature and the expertise available within the consortium. The five project topics were defined: project 1. protocol cleaning assessment paintings under Ultraviolet illumination; project 2. protocol cleaning assessment metal – silver; project 3. consolidation of archaeological iron and copper; project 4. consolidation of metals/glass/ceramics in a non-invasive way; project 5. assessment of cleaning and consolidation treatments with Laser Speckle Imaging (LSI).

Projects 3 and 4 were found to be unsuitable for effective assessment using low-tech methodologies, and so far only high-tech approaches such as X-ray tomography or neutron tomography provide depth information. The impermeability of materials like metal and ceramics to light complicates the application of alternative low-tech methods. Based on the findings from Project 5, the consolidation of crizzled and delaminated glass will be further investigated using LSI. However, this testing lies beyond the scope of the current deliverable. Ultimately, projects 1, 2, and 5 have shown promise for further development and are presented in this report. The protocols described in the report make use of and builds on the deliverable D5.1 “Protocols for cross-consortium validation of solutions”, that describes the link between these methodologies and the new analytical methodologies developed as part of the GoGreen project.

Green Evaluation and implications

The environmental impact of conservation analytical techniques is considered in assessment and choice of materials, energy consumption and efficiency, digital sobriety, and circular economy. Additionally, techniques considered should be economically and geographically accessible. Low tech methods provide socio-economic sustainability benefits, as well as low energy consumption and reduced material use. The techniques evaluated here compare the efficacy of low tech analysis which can improve sustainability of conservation globally while ensuring that the results are still of the highest professional standards. Evaluation of materials according to the GoGreen Green Definition Parameters ([see website](#)) and considerations regarding reuse (i.e. samples, mockups, coupons, photographic supports/backgrounds, etc.) and procurement evaluations of equipment used supports greener decisions for conservation diagnostics and analysis. Additional considerations around digital sobriety include number of images and duration of data storage.

2. Protocol cleaning assessment paintings under Ultraviolet illumination (project 1)

2.1 Concept

The aim of this project is to develop an approach to study varnishes during the preliminary examination and varnish removal treatment. The approach is a low-tech alternative to multispectral Ultraviolet (UV)-induced luminescence imaging (Ramaciotti, 2023). To make the approach low-tech, the equipment must be sufficiently low-cost, low energy consumption, easily accessible and require little knowledge to operate.

Currently, painting conservators use UV-induced luminescence viewing with a handheld UV torch as a low-tech method for evaluating varnish removal. Aged natural resin varnishes typically exhibit intense green fluorescence under UV light, while the underlying paint layer, usually bound with linseed oil, fluoresces less intensely. When varnish is removed, this appears as a darker region under UV, lacking the bluish-green fluorescence, thus enhancing the visual contrast between varnished and unvarnished areas compared to normal light. While this practice is useful, it has limitations. For instance, varnish residues might be overlooked in areas where the contrast between areas with and without varnish is weak. Moreover, the current method primarily provides information on the spatial distribution of varnish, offering little insight into variations in varnish thickness or type.

These shortcomings are mainly due to three factors: the use of broad-band light sources that emit violet light outside the UV range (above 400 nm); the viewing of UV luminescence in the presence of ambient light, rather than in a completely dark room; and the underutilization of filters. Currently, the only filters used during UV observation are UV protection glasses for safety. The proposed protocol addresses these issues by offering a more refined approach to UV-induced luminescence viewing, potentially providing more detailed information.

Excitation and emission wavelengths of UV-induced photoluminescence has been used for in-depth analysis of painted or varnished surfaces by various researchers in the past two decades. Several studies focused on pigment differentiation (Pronti, 2006, Comelli, 2007, and Pelagotti, 2007), in which the excitation wavelength was 365 nm, and emission wavelengths were filtered to increments as small as 10 nm (Pronti and Comelli). Ramaciotti (2023) and Cavaleri (2020) have focused on varnishes. Ramaciotti experimented with both the excitation wavelengths and emission wavelengths for the optimal documentation of varnish removal. Cavaleri experimented with different excitation wavelengths and captured the entire visible spectrum for evaluation of aged, pigmented varnishes typically used on wood instruments. For more low-tech, practical applications in the conservator's studio, Cosentino (2015) has compared UV-induced photoluminescence with two different excitation wavelengths of either 245 nm or 365 nm and captured in the entire visible spectrum. To the best of our knowledge, experimentation with color filters for viewing UV-induced photoluminescence with the human eye has not been conducted in the field of cultural heritage thus far. The research question for this proof-of-principle study is, "how can the use of color filters enhance the viewing of varnished paintings with the purpose of understanding their composition and/ or varnish removal efficacy?" The sub-questions focus on the impact of underlying layers on the observed fluorescence, the variability in appearance of photoluminescence of different varnishes, and the difference in perception between filtered and unfiltered UV-induced luminescence when viewed by the eye versus captured by a camera.

The protocol considers operator safety by including UV protection glasses within the protocol. Through introducing the idea of using different filters for viewing under UV, there is a possibility that the protocol may encourage increased UV exposure for the object. The protocol is low-cost and low in energy consumption. It uses items commonly available in the conservation studio. The color filters required in the protocol, have a one-off cost of 70 euros (as of September 2024), making it accessible to more users than other methods for observation of multispectral UV-induced photoluminescence. It can reduce the need for transport of the painting of interest to a laboratory with analytical instruments, or the transport of portable, high-tech

analytical equipment to the conservation studio. The protocol does not generate heavy digital data that necessitates storage.

2.2 Experimental Set-up

The protocol being tested in this deliverable is for observation with the human eye using filters. To provide objective information to support qualitative observations from viewing with the eye, we conducted two types of experiments: 1. Using 'off-the-shelf' cameras to document UV-induced photoluminescence and 2. Observing the same photoluminescence with the human eye. In both experiments, the same filters and the same samples were used, except the UV safety glasses, which were only used in the latter experiment.

Samples

Seven samples were chosen for the study: a varnished oil painting on a wooden panel with a heterogenous composition, one mock-up with monochromatic paint stripes covered with different varnishes, four monochrome reconstructions covered with Laropal A81 and dammar varnishes, and a mock-up with various natural resin varnishes is included. For more details, see Section IV: Sample description.

Imaging experiment with an 'off-the-shelf' camera

All seven samples were photographed with six different 1.25-inch (3.18 cm) color filters and without any filter. These filters cover different ranges of the visible light spectrum. The colors were violet, light blue, green, yellow, red and dark red. The transmission spectra of these filters can be found in Appendix III. A 1.25" - 2" adaptor ring (ZWO) was used in combination with step-up rings to fix the color filters in front of the lens. The color filters were screwed on and off as necessary. A Nikon D750 camera (unknown purchase date) was used, for all samples except Sample 7, due to equipment availability. The parameters were set to f/11 and ISO 200. Exposure was dependent on the intensity of luminescence. Sample 7 was imaged with a SONY ILCE 7CM2 camera (unknown purchase date). All samples were illuminated with two ZERO 200/2 (IP65) lamps from Helling GmbH, except for Sample 7. All imaging was carried out in a dark room with no stray light. The samples were placed vertically on an easel. These stationary lamps were placed at an approximate distance of 40 cm from the sample, at an angle of approximately 45 degrees on either side.

Another set of images for Samples 1, 2, and 7 were captured with one Jaxman U1C 18650 handheld UV torch. The handheld UV torch was held by hand at an approximate distance of 60 cm from the samples, at an angle of approximately 80 degrees (almost frontal), from the proper right side of the sample. The technical details of both UV light sources are found in Appendix III.

Viewing experiment with UV protection lenses and color filters

All seven samples were viewed by the author of this project report under illumination with the handheld UV torch emitting radiation with a peak at 365 nm, in a dark room with no stray light, while wearing Bollé UV protection glasses for safety (product reference code: VIPCI) (Figure 1). These glasses are covered with duct tape to minimize the impact of the light source, which can render the photoluminescence of the sample imperceptible. The same color filters used for the imaging experiment were held in front of the gap in the duct tape (the right lens). The choice between right and left was arbitrary. The observation alternated between filtered viewing and unfiltered viewing (full visible spectrum, still with UV protection glasses) to allow for comparisons between the two. The author has received prior training as a painting conservator and is accustomed to viewing UV-induced photoluminescence of paintings. She has no vision impairments. The

author moved freely to illuminate different parts of the samples. The distances between the samples and the light source or the author were not fixed.

Figure 1. Image of UV protection glasses, covered with duct tape (left). Color filters used in the experiment (right).

2.3 Methodological Approach

For the imaging experiment, images captured with and without filters were compared against each other. The images were compared on a qualitative basis following the two criteria: ease of readability (contrast) and additional information gained. The observations focus primarily on the varnish presence and absence, rather than the underlying paint. The qualitative observations during the ‘viewing with the eye’ experiment was documented in handwritten notes. These observations were also focused on the two aforementioned criteria. The filter set was chosen from a commercial set of color filters that have a varied set of colors with minimal distortion. High quality, narrow-bandwidth filters that are used in the multispectral UV-induced photoluminescence set-up in Deliverable 3.2 were not used. Such filters are not considered as low-tech, due to their expensive price and consequently, low accessibility. In the preliminary stage, color films commonly used to alter lighting in entertainment venues were considered. However, their visibility was significantly lower compared to glass filters, so they were excluded from the study. A previous study established that the spectra obtained from a varnished, painted surface under UV radiation result from a combination of the varnish's fluorescence and the reflection of this visible light by the underlying paint layer (Elias et al., 2009). They also observed that the UV light reflected by the varnish and the paint layer is negligible. Therefore, samples with a variety of underlying paint colors and overlying varnishes were chosen.

2.4 Description of the object/mock-ups

An overview of the samples is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of samples.

Sample	Varnish type	Underlying paint media; color
1 Panel painting	Dammar	Linseed oil; heterogenous
2 Mock-up with varied varnishes on synthetic paint	10 different varnishes	Medium unknown; white, blue, brown, black
3 Zinc white in oil	Dammar and Laropal A81	Linseed oil
4 Zinc white in egg tempera	Dammar and Laropal A81	Linseed oil
5 Burnt sienna in oil	Dammar and Laropal A81	Linseed oil
6 Burnt Sienna in egg tempera	Dammar and Laropal A81	Linseed oil
7 Mock-up prepared by Stols-Witlox	7 different natural resin varnishes	Medium unknown; white, blue, light blue, black

Sample 1: Panel painting

Sample 1 is a study painting obtained from the painting conservation studio of the Rijksmuseum (Figure 2). It has a wood substrate, possible sizing layer, ground layer with chalk, gypsum and lead bound in (linseed) oil, brown layer with earth pigments bound in (linseed) oil, paint layer in (linseed) oil. It contains dammar varnish, applied in 1985 under unknown circumstances. There are also small circular areas where varnish has been removed, in the style of cleaning tests. Production and treatment dates unknown, and documentation relating to this object does not exist. For a more detailed description of the panel painting, see Appendix IV. Materials which present UV-induced luminescence in this sample include the varnish, linseed oil, lead white (Pronti, et al., 2017), madder lake, vermillion and red lead. Madder lake is known to brightly fluoresce in red with a broad range of excitation wavelengths between 250-580 nm (Milani et al., 1980). Vermillion and red lead, on the other hand, are noted to show a dark red fluorescence when excited with long-wave UV (Stuart, 2007).

Figure 2. Visible light image of Sample 1.

Sample 2: Mock-up with varied varnishes on synthetic paint

Sample 2 is a mock-up of different types of natural and synthetic varnishes applied on painted cardboard (Figure 3). Paint build up and binding medium are unknown. The composition of the varnishes is from left to right: 1) Dammar in Shellsol A and Shellsol D40, 2) Dammar and wax in Shellsol D40, 3) MS2A, 4) MS2A and wax, 5) Regalrez, 6) Regalrez and wax, 7) Laropal, 8) Laropal wax, 9) Paraloid B72 in 50 xylene 50 Shellsol A, 10) Paraloid B72, 11) unvarnished. The mock-up is owned by the painting conservation studio of the Rijksmuseum.

Figure 3. Visible light image of Sample 2.

Samples 3, 4, 5 and 6: Monochrome reconstructions

The Samples 3-6 are reconstructions that were produced in GoGreen task 3.1, and the specific details of production can be found in Deliverables 3.1 (paint layer) and 3.2 (varnish) (Figure 4). From left to right: Sample 3 contains zinc white in oil, Sample 4 contains zinc white in egg tempera, Sample 5 contains burnt sienna in oil and Sample 6 is composed of burnt sienna in egg tempera. All four samples are varnished with two types of varnishes: a 20% (w/v) Laropal A81 varnish in 2:3 Shellsol A100: Shellsol D40 and a 20% (w/v) dammar varnish in 17:83 Shellsol A100:Shellsol D40 (Figure 4). Burnt sienna does not fluoresce under UV radiation, and zinc white is known to fluoresce under UV radiation.

Figure 4. From left to right, visible light images of Samples 3 (zinc white in oil), 4 (zinc white in egg tempera), 5 (burnt sienna in oil), and 6 (burnt sienna in egg tempera). Especially visible in Samples 5 and 6 are pale brown areas, where the varnish is absent. This includes small patches of varnish removal tests, conducted in Deliverable 3.2 using various solvents.

Sample 7: Mock-up prepared by Stols-Witlox, with various natural resin varnishes

Sample 7 was produced as part of the Art History master's dissertation by Maartje Stols-Witlox (1995) (Figure 5). The composition of the varnish layers is from left to right: sandarac varnish, sandarac varnish (heated preparation), mastic varnish, combined varnish with sandarac and mastic, manila copal varnish, shellac containing varnish, manila copal varnish with rosemary oil. Details regarding the varnishes can be found in Stols-Witlox, 1995.

Figure 5. Visible light image of Sample 7. Dark corners due to adaptor rings used on the camera.

2.5 Results of experiments with object/mock-ups

Samples 1-7 are investigated with the ‘imaging experiment with an *off-the-shelf* camera’ (imaging experiment) and the ‘viewing with the eye’ experiment. The images captured with the ‘off-the-shelf’ camera are found in Appendix I. The exposure times required for capturing the images in Appendix I are given in Table 2. When multiple images of the same sample are captured using the same filter but with varying exposure times, only the images that exhibit adequate brightness without signs of overexposure are included in the analysis. Brightness was evaluated subjectively. As seen in Table 2, exposure times vary significantly between filters as well as between samples. It is observed that the exposure times are consistently longer when using the handheld UV torch compared to the stationary UV lamp. For Sample 2, the images captured with the dark red filter were underexposed, suggesting that extended exposure times may have improved image quality. This issue was present with both the handheld UV torch and the stationary lamp. The same was noted for Samples 5 and 6, whose exposure time was 56.4 seconds for the dark red filter. Due to the camera’s settings, it was not possible to specify an exposure time longer than 30 seconds.

Table 2. Exposure in seconds of the images taken with the NIKON D750 camera.

Sample	Exposure time for each filter (in seconds)						
	Violet	Light blue	Green	Yellow	Red	Dark red	No filter
1 Panel	5	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	6	1
2 Mock-up*	13	4	6	10	30	30**	6
2 Mock-up	6	2	4	6	20	20**	1
3, 4 Zinc white samples	20	4	6	4	4	20	1
5, 6 Burnt sienna samples	8	10	15	10	20	56.4**	62.8+
7 Mock-up by Stols-Witlox (SONY)*	2.5	0.5	1.6	1.3	1.6	10	0.62

* Where light source is the handheld UV torch. All other images were taken with the stationary lamp.

Cells are coloured in grey where it was deemed “too dark” when viewing with eyes. The Stols-Witlox Mock-up was imaged with the SONY ILCE 7CM2 camera.

Table 3. Perceived luminosity of UV-induced photoluminescence when viewing with the eye with the handheld UV torch.

Sample	Perceived level of luminosity when using each filter						
	Violet	Light blue	Green	Yellow	Red	Dark red	No filter
1 Panel	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Dark	Sufficient
2 Mock-up	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Too dark	Sufficient
3 Zinc white- oil	Too dark	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Dark	Sufficient
4 Zinc white-egg tempera	Too dark	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Dark	Sufficient
5 Burnt sienna-oil	Too dark	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Too dark	Sufficient
6 Burnt sienna-egg tempera	Too dark	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Too dark	Too dark	Sufficient
7 Mock-up by Stols-Witlox	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient	Too dark	Sufficient

Descriptors used: too bright, sufficient, dark, and too dark.

The observations from the ‘viewing with the eye’ experiment, summarizing the perceived luminosity of the fluorescence, are presented in Table 3. The perceived luminosity is categorized into four levels: too bright, sufficient, dark, and too dark. No sample was evaluated to be too bright. Additional qualitative observations

about the contrast between areas with and without varnish and any additional observations can be found in Appendix II. In summary, no filter consistently provided an improved viewing experience compared to viewing without a filter. When viewing with the eye, the eyes needed to adjust to viewing in dark conditions. Therefore, eliminating all other sources of light was crucial. The eye could quickly adapt to detecting patterns in different colors, and the varying tints were less distracting than anticipated. There are two discrepancies between the camera-captured images and visual observations. First, on the mock-up with synthetic paint (Sample 2), faint fluorescence of certain varnishes applied to the black strip of paint was visible to the naked eye when using green and yellow filters. However, this fluorescence was not detectable in any of the photographs. Second, the yellow filter provided better visual contrast between partially removed and intact varnish to the eye, compared to the contrast observed in the corresponding camera image. Aside from these differences, the camera images generally represented the visual experience observed with the naked eye.

A noticeable variation in contrast is observed with the use of different filters. In the panel painting (Sample 1), the light blue filter significantly enhanced the contrast between varnished and non-varnished areas compared to the unfiltered image. For the mock-up with varied varnishes on synthetic paint (Sample 2), the yellow and red filters improved contrast relative to the unfiltered image. In the zinc white reconstructions (Samples 3,4), the light blue filter enhanced contrast, whereas no filter improved contrast in the burnt sienna reconstructions (Samples 5,6). For the mock-up by Stols-Witlox (Sample 7), the green, yellow, and red filters were effective in enhancing contrast. Across all seven samples, the dark red and violet filters consistently diminished the contrast between varnished and non-varnished areas.

Several examples demonstrate the additional information obtained from using specific filters. In the panel painting (Sample 1), the red color in one of the cleaned patches is more prominent visible under the yellow filter (Figure 6). Additionally, damages and irregularities in the skin tones are more pronounced under the dark red filter (Figure 6). For the mock-up (Sample 2), the green filter enhances the definition of brush strokes on the blue paint strip (Figure 7), and the contrast *between* different varnishes is more distinct under the yellow filter (Figure 8). In the zinc white reconstructions (Sample 3,4), the violet, light blue, green and yellow filters achieved additional information. The violet filter emphasizes a patch of bluish fluorescence in the Laropal A81 varnish, while the green and yellow filters enhance the contrast between varnishes. The yellow filter also makes the marks along the left edge of the reconstruction more noticeable. However, no additional information was gained from color filters in the burnt sienna reconstructions. In the mock-up Stols-Witlox (Sample 7) the yellow filter made the heterogeneity within each varnish type more evident (Figure 9).

Figure 6. The panel painting imaged with the yellow filter (left), without a filter (middle) and the red filter (right). The red color in the right circle where varnish is absent stands out in the yellow filter. The marks in the skin stand out more in the red filter than without a filter.

Figure 7. The second horizontal strip of paint has more defined brushstrokes when viewed with the green filter (right) than without any filter (left).

Figure 8. The varnishes as they appear in the bottom strip show more heterogeneity between the varnishes with the yellow filter (right) than without any filter (left).

Figure 9. Brushstrokes in the varnish or heterogeneity within each varnish were first noticed when seen on the image captured with the yellow filter (right) than without any filter.

Contrast and additional details achieved through color filters

Images captured with and without color filters were compared on two criteria: contrast and additional details obtained. The results demonstrated that, in some cases, color filters enhanced the contrast between varnished and non-varnished areas, as well as between different types of varnishes. However, in many instances, the information provided by the filters was comparable to that obtained without their use.

In GoGreen's deliverable 3.2, Cazals (CNRS) uses narrow-bandwidth monochromatic filters for multispectral UV-induced photoluminescence imaging. In the set-up used, the excitation and emission wavelengths are adjusted to increase the contrast between varnishes and the underlying paint bound in linseed oil. Fluorescence spectra of natural resin varnishes have an emission maximum around 400-450 nm, while linseed oil has an emission maximum around 480 nm and shifts to longer wavelengths as it ages (Cairns, 2020). Cazals uses green monochromatic filters with bandwidth to enhance the contrast between varnish and underlying paint. The green filter utilized to enhance contrast in Sample 7 in this study exhibits a broader bandwidth compared to the filter employed in study by Cazals. Specifically, it has a full width at half maximum

(FWHM) of 75 nm, with a peak transmission at 530 nm. However, we do not attribute the observed contrast between varnish and oil paint to the filtering effect of the green filter, as the bandwidth used in our study is considerably wider than that of study by Cazals (FWHM of 20 nm). Instead, we propose that the enhanced contrast may be explained by the human eye's increased sensitivity to green wavelengths (Goldstein, 2013). The filters enable comparison of fluorescence intensity in different regions of the visible spectrum. If a material appears dark through the green filter, the material does not fluoresce in green or does so only weakly. This could also be inferred from observing red photoluminescence without a filter. However, using color filters allows for a quicker assessment of materials with different types of fluorescence characteristics.

Camera versus viewing with the eye

The captured images serve as adequate representations of the experience of viewing with the eye. Also, it helped with the discovery of weakly fluorescent varnish strips that the camera did not capture in the experiment. Exposure times for the camera do not directly apply to the human eye. Even when the camera required over 10 seconds of exposure to capture weaker photoluminescence, the eye could still detect it. For very weak photoluminescence, the camera, with a longer exposure, can capture more details than the eye. Viewing through the eye prompted the author to approach the sample more closely, due to the darker view and smaller field of vision. This may help in identifying details that could be missed when viewing a full-size image on a screen. Similarly, looking back and forth between different color filters led to focusing on particular details that stand out most. Therefore, the focus of the viewer shifts in a different way than when viewing without any filters. As a painting conservator, the author is accustomed to looking for interesting features under UV light. This feature may be a purely visible anomaly. It can also be a discrepancy from expected luminescence behavior of materials. For example, it is well known that darker areas of a linseed oil-bound painting, containing earth pigments, tend to appear dark under UV. If it were luminescing in an unexpected way, this will alert the conservator to investigate further. Also, the conservator has a profound understanding of the stratigraphy of paintings, and which materials are expected to be encountered for each layer. Observation is therefore a highly proactive and interactive process, where new hypotheses arise and are verified one after another. This approach is fundamentally the same between viewing photos or observing with the eye. The former does allow for digital post-processing, which can enhance contrast or create composite images as one does with false color infrared images (Cultural Heritage Science Open Source, 2024). It should be noted that there may be subtle differences between commercial cameras, as each camera processes reflectance differently. Comparison between the NIKON D750 camera and SONY ILCE 7CM2 was not possible as the cameras were used on different samples.

Exposure times required for the imaging experiment

The intensity of UV-induced photoluminescence in varnishes varied significantly between different color filters, as reflected in the exposure times. For instance, the dark red filter consistently required longer exposure than the green filter, indicating weaker photoluminescence in the red region. This can be explained by either the fluorescence spectra of varnishes, whose emission maximum is around 400-450 nm and becomes significantly less in the red region (Appendix V). An alternative explanation is that most samples did not have red paint layers. Therefore, any red fluorescence from the varnish was not reflected by the underlying paint layer. Second, there was notable variability in photoluminescence intensity among different samples, with burnt sienna needing longer exposure than zinc white. Imaging without a filter consistently required the shortest exposure time.

By observing under consistent conditions, it is possible to assess the fluorescence intensity. For instance, capturing the mock-up with the red filter required a 20-second exposure, compared to six seconds for

the panel painting. This difference is attributed to the mock-up's white underlying layer, which reflects fluorescence more efficiently than the panel painting. Both samples required a 1-second exposure to capture photoluminescence, highlighting the value of color filters in obtaining this information. It should be taken into account that the photoluminescence intensity is not equivalent to the fluorescence intensity of the varnish. This is because the photoluminescence observed is an amalgamation of the fluorescence of the varnish layer as well as the reflectance of this fluorescence by the underlying pictorial layer (Elias et al., 2009). Therefore, fluorescence of a sample with a dark pictorial layer cannot be compared with that of a light-colored pictorial layer. Consequently, on a sample with a red pictorial layer, it can be expected that the fluorescence intensity through the red filter will be stronger than if the pictorial layer were blue.

With visible light photography, color calibration charts are used for post-processing according to the light source and its intensity. With UV photography, there is no standard calibration method. However, a calibration method to ensure that images captured with different filters still have the same level of brightness would be beneficial. In the same vein, exposure times are likely not replicable, if imaged with a different RGB color camera than the NIKOND750 used in the experiment. The relative length will stay the same, i.e., if the red filter takes longer than the green filter on one camera, this will be the case when using another camera.

2.6 Test user-group feedback

A feedback session was held with 3 painting conservators and 2 conservation scientists. The paintings used were the Rubens sketch with dammar and Laropal A81 varnishes produced by The Courtauld Institute and a painting with dammar varnish from University of Bologna. It was noted that some conservators found the viewing with one eye disconcerting. There were positive responses to the general ease of usage. Green and yellow filters were preferred to the red and dark red filters. The light blue and violet filters were not favoured. Some articulated that the green and yellow filters seem to enhance the contrast between areas where varnish was removed and where the varnish remained. This is in agreement with the viewing experience of the author on the mock-up with synthetic paint and the mock-up by Stols-Witlox (Sample 7). Additionally, because varnish fluoresces weaker in the red region, viewing through a red filter results in a darker image than with a green filter. This serves as an explanation for the lack of popularity of the former.

2.7 Summary of protocol

Regardless of the situation, whether it be observing varnish or pigments, or any surface that is expected to fluoresce, the following protocol can be followed. The following items are required: UV protection glasses, a set of six Omegon color filters (#47, #82A, #12, #21, #25, #56), a Jaxman handheld UV lamp or other UV lamp, and duct tape. Apply duct tape to cover the majority of the UV protection glasses, leaving a small aperture for viewing through a color filter. It is sensible to omit the violet and dark red filters, as they were consistently too dim for visual observation. Position the object of interest in a darkened environment or dark room, arrange the filters within reach, and activate the UV light to observe fluorescence.

Regarding lamps, while handheld options like the Jaxman UV lamp can suffice, a stationary lamp with uniform illumination may be more convenient. Handheld lamps require consideration of the distance, which is less of an issue with stationary lamps. Light sources that emit violet light affect the appearance of the photoluminescence and should be avoided. With such lamps, using color filters that block violet light (any filter except violet and light blue) may be beneficial.

2.8 Protocol limitations and advances

A disadvantage of the proposed protocol is that it can only be used in a dark room. Particularly weakly fluorescent varnishes with a fluorescence quenching underlying paint layer, or any dark paint layer, may yield little result. An advantage is the simplicity of use, the low cost of the filters, and that it does not require expert

knowledge. Additionally, in comparison to taking a photo, viewing with the eyes may take longer time, and lead to longer UV exposure times. The eye can adjust to viewing at ca. 10 cm away, to see features of 0.5 mm, but it may not be practical to do so. The resolution achieved with the protocol is therefore inferior to that of a camera, which often have superior magnifying functions.

2.9 Conclusions and next steps

Several conclusions can be drawn from the experience of viewing with the eye. First, the use of monochromatic filters does not impede pattern recognition. Observations remain consistent whether using red, green, or yellow filters. Similar to the adaptation process with other monochromatic imaging modalities, such as X-radiographs, practitioners can become proficient with these viewing techniques through experience. Above all, it is greener and more accessible.

This study explored the potential of commercial color filters for enhancing the viewing of UV-induced photoluminescence in varnishes. While the experiment revealed some benefits for assessing varnish heterogeneity and documenting fluorescence intensity, the practical advantages appear limited. The traditional method of viewing UV-induced photoluminescence without filters allows for use in non-dark environments, which is a significant benefit. Filtered viewing reduces photoluminescence intensity, making it unsuitable for non-dark environments and restricting its use to dark rooms. Therefore, a compelling incentive, such as improved varnish removal evaluation, would be necessary for broader adoption. Commercial color filters have lower rates of transmission than high-tech filters. However, the experiment demonstrated that they could still be useful for viewing with the eye. For materials with characteristic UV-induced emissions in certain colors, these filters could help these differences stand out more. Additionally, in cases where underlying paint fluoresces in green or blue—overlapping with the peak fluorescence region of the varnish—a red filter or another filter outside this region could be beneficial.

Next steps involve testing with additional color filters, such as orange, which may provide further benefits through experimental investigation. Tests should be implemented to explore intra-viewer differences. Secondly, employing color-filtered lenses for both eyes, rather than just one, may enhance the visual experience. Development of calibration methods for use with color filters will be useful. Additionally, there is potential to explore the use of these filters for magnified or microscopic viewing.

The current protocol encourages viewing without relying on the digital innovations. However, with regards to potential digital developments, it may be possible to digitally construct color-filtered images through post-processing. This can then be applied to AR lenses to still maintain the “viewing with the eye” experience. It may also be fruitful to apply post-processing to images captured with color filters to enhance contrast, or to compare with larger data sets with the aid of machine learning.

3. Protocol cleaning assessment metal – silver (project 2)

3.1 Concept

This project aims to develop a low-tech approach for the assessment of cleaning efficiency on metal substrates, with a focus on polished or semi-polished silver surfaces. It included two parts: (i) using a normal camera for acquisition of conventional photos for highly reflective metal surfaces; (ii) using the reflective transformation imaging (RTI) technique for observing possible surface damages (e.g., scratching) after cleaning.

The acquisition of conventional photos for highly reflective surfaces such as a polished silver surface is challenging, due to strong light reflection from the surface, which covers surface details, and also due to reflection of the camera lens, leading to a dark area in the middle of the photos. Part (i) of this project aims to provide a complete protocol for the photo acquisition using easily assessable devices and have low energy consumption. At the same time, such photos are expected to be used as supportive data for the characterisation of silver tarnish that was artificially created with the green aging method developed in GoGreen (Wu et al. 2024-1; Wu et al. 2024-2).

RTI is a technique of computational photography, which helps to visualize and enhance details of an object's surface that are barely visible through conventional photography (Dittus 2016). The working principle of RTI is based on the Polynomial Texture Maps (PTM) principle (Malzbender et al. 2001). It is also a non-invasive method that is capable of investigating surface deformations and textures, widely used in studies of heritage objects such as paintings, archaeological artefacts, glass and metal objects, architecture, etc. (Di Lorio et al. 2024; Dittus 2016; Mytum and Peterson 2018; Kotoula and Earl 2014; Cosentino et al. 2015). The generation of a RTI file involves producing a sequence of photos, during which the object and camera are at a fixed position, while the angle of illumination changes. Each photo is then produced under the illumination of a point light source at a known position. A schematic illustration showing the light positions is presented in Figure 10. There are two common methods for RTI: highlight-reflectance transformation imaging (H-RTI) and the light array. The H-RTI requires equipment generally available in museums, including a tripod, a fixed camera, two reflecting spheres, a string and a light source.¹ The light array method uses a black and matte dome where illumination is obtained by light sources fixed at known positions; a software uses the known positions of the light to create a light plan, which maps the angle of the light, associating each image with the lighting angle (Piquette 2011). The light array method is used in the current project. It is good to mention that the RTI has a larger digital footprint because many photos under different lighting are taken. The approach using a regular camera for conventional photos is therefore a greener alternative since fewer photos are taken.

¹Information obtained from an internal report “Practical guide – Reflectance Transformation Imaging” by Rebecca Rochat (2017), HE-Arc CR.

Figure 10. Virtual dome showing light positions for recording the necessary photographs with the corresponding light reflections in the black sphere and setup for RTIs. Reproduced from (Dittus 2016).

Soft metals such as silver could be damaged by some cleaning materials, showing surface damages such as scratches or pitting. As an alternative technique of optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), RTI are expected to provide surface details after cleaning, with a much larger view. In part (ii) of this project, RTI is used as a supporting technique for the assessment of selected benchmark methods in GoGreen for the cleaning of tarnished silver coupons.

3.2 Experimental Set-up

Experimental set-ups for conventional photo acquisition

Conventional photo acquisition for reflective metal surfaces was performed using a *Canon 600D* camera and a *Canon 18-55 mm* lens. A *Dörr* digital HD slim polarizer filter (58 mm) was mounted on the front of the lens. During the acquisition, the camera was mounted either on a *HAISER profite 5000* reproduction table or on a *Manfrotto* portable camera stative. Two *HAISER RB 5004 HF* lamps are attached on the reproduction table.

Acquisition with a reproduction table

The reproduction table is recommended, because its settings can be easily adjusted and recorded, and thus the acquisition is more reproducible. The reproduction table employed in this project and the schematic illustration of its structure are presented in Figure 11a, b. The camera height, lamp holder angle (Θ), lamp height² and lamp directions (e.g., facing up or down, left or right) are adjusted and fixed with grub screws.

² For brevity, in the schematic illustration the lamp holder has levels of 1 to 10, which represents the lamp height. On the real lamp holder, levels of 1 to 17 were marked. Each level equals 3 cm.

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Figure 11. (a) Reproduction table used during the photo acquisition; (b) schematic illustration of settings of a reproduction table; (c) polarizer filter used for photo acquisition of reflective surfaces.

During the acquisition with the reproduction table, the height of the camera was fixed at 23 cm. For a highly reflective metal surface such as the polished copper and brass coupons shown in Figure 12b, c, the lamp angle Θ was set to ca. 5° and the lamp height was on the level 6, with two lamps facing down. For camera settings it is suggested using a shorter exposure time (e.g., 1/60 s) and a higher focal length (e.g., f11) and lower light sensitivity (e.g., ISO 100), in order to reduce the intensity of the reflected light from the metal surface and avoid grainy photos. For the photo acquisition of a relatively matte metal surface such as an unpolished silver coupon shown in Figure 12a, a longer exposure time (e.g., 1/30 s) and a higher focal length (e.g., f9) are recommended. The light sensitivity can be kept the same. At the same time, the lamp holder angle Θ was set to the middle position of $0-45^\circ$ (ca. 22°) and the lamp height was on the level 4. The direction of the lamps was adjusted facing towards each other. The same settings can also be used for the acquisition of tarnished metal coupons with a polished surface, on which a certain level of metal gloss is still retained.

Figure 12. Conventional photos with the polarizer filter of unaged and aged appearances of unpolished silver coupons (a), polished copper coupons (b) and polished brass coupons (c).

A disadvantage of using the reproduction table lies in its limited focal area, which leads to a limited number of coupons within one photo. The main reason lies in the light reflection of the camera lens, which mostly affects the coupons in the middle area of the photo (i.e., they appear darker than others). Even with the polarizer filter, such reflection cannot be fully avoided. In order to include more coupons within one photo, one option could be changing the photo orientation. For example, for the acquisition of seven semi-polished silver coupons (1 unaged reference coupon + 6 cleaned coupons as shown in Figure 13), a photo was first taken with the vertical orientation (a) and then changed to the horizontal direction during the photo processing (b). Also, the lamp holder angle Θ was set to almost 0° and the camera was tilted inwards about 2° . With such settings, significant camera reflection can be avoided, but some colour distortion (e.g., some coupons are more yellowish than the others) caused by uneven lighting cannot be fully avoided.

Figure 13. (a) Photo obtained with a vertical orientation; (b) photo orientation adjusted by rotating.

Acquisition with a portable camera stative

During the acquisition with a portable stative, the coupon batches were placed on a normal table, with two table lamps facing each other. The lamps were placed either with some distance (ca. 1 m) or very close (lamp shades touching each other), resulting in different lighting conditions. The camera was tilted forward by ca. 5 °, in order to avoid significant light reflection of the lens. For photos of single coupons that were placed on a black background, the same camera settings as those used for the acquisition inside of the dome for RTI were used.

Experimental set-ups for RTI

A *Broncolor Scope D50* dome, mounted with 48 LED lights on different positions of the inner wall of the dome, was employed for the RTI of the same set of silver coupons in part (i) (Figure 14). For RTI, a 18-55 mm lens is not sufficient for high-quality photos, therefore a *Canon 700D* camera with a *Canon 60 mm* lens was used. The Dörr polarizer filter was mounted in front of the lens. The camera was stabilized with a camera holder on top of the dome, with the lens facing down. The camera holder was adjusted to make the lens slightly above the top opening of the dome. Samples were placed above a black *Canson* drawing paper on a manual jack inside of the dome, directly below the camera lens. The height of manual jack was 13 cm from its upper edge to the table on which the dome was placed. Photos were acquired under the visual light (400-700 nm) in sequence with the LED lights (LED1 to LED48) in the remote mode with *EOS Utility* software. Camera settings included an exposure time of 1/50 s, focal length of f7.1, light sensitivity of ISO200 and white balance of 5200 K (equivalent to day light). In order to reduce the light reflection from silver surfaces, the LED light intensity was set to 5. A complete acquisition of 48 photos was required for the RTI processing with *Authentica Creator* software. Important technical parameters with the software included directional light intensity, material intensity of the object, diffuse intensity, sharpness and global intensity. An internal report regarding the acquisition of silver objects and surfaces with RTI at HE-Arc CR was used as a reference user guide.³

³ The report was written by Alexandra Lefebvre for the project *d'acquisition Imagerie à transformation (DoITR)*.

Figure 14. (a) Broncolor Scope D50 dome used in the project; (b) a Canon 700D camera mounted on top of the dome with a camera holder; (c) interface of the RTI software Authentica Creator.

3.3 Methodological Approach

Samples

Some silver coupons, namely the S2 coupons in the metal test systems constructed in GoGreen, were used for both conventional photo acquisition and RTI. Such coupons have a size of 20x20x0.5 mm and were semi-polished by the manufacturer.⁴ They were first aged with the albumin solution method (AS), a green aging method developed in GoGreen, for 10 h and 3 h for obtaining strong tarnish and light tarnish respectively, and then cleaned with the selected benchmark methods, including two commercial products (i.e., Hagerty silver polish cream and Hagerty silver polish cloth) and two non-commercial products (i.e., a CaCO₃ slurry and its diluted version). It is worth noting that the cleaning directions (i.e., directions of swabbing with the slurries/cream or rubbing with the polish cloth) were perpendicular to the fine rolling marks that were formed during the manufacture of the coupons, so that the scratches caused by the benchmarks can be more easily identified. Details about the selection and performance of the benchmarks on tarnished silver coupons are presented in GoGreen deliverable D3.2. The aging conditions, benchmarks, and imaging methods employed for individual coupons are presented in Table 4. Two unaged coupons (i.e., SS2-045, SP2-045) were used as references.

Table 4. Silver samples used for the imaging methods. “SP” refers to pure silver; “SS” refers to sterling silver.

Coupon type		Aging method	Tarnish condition	Cleaning method	Conventional photo		RTI	
Sterling silver	Pure silver				Tarnished side	Cleaned side	Tarnished side	Cleaned side
SS2-045 (ref)	SP2-045 (ref)	Non-aged	-	-	✓	☐	☐	☐
SS2-033 to SS2-035	SP2-033 to SP2-035	AS for 10 h	Strong	CaCO ₃ slurry	☐	☐	SS2-035	SS2-035
SS2-036 to SS2-038	SS2-036 to SP2-038	AS for 10 h	Strong	Hagerty polish cream	☐	☐	-	SS2-038
SS2-039 to SS2-041	SP2-039 to SP2-041	AS for 3 h	Light	Hagerty polish cloth	☐	☐	SS2-041	SS2-041
SS2-042 to SS2-044	SP2-042 to SP2-044	AS for 3 h	Light	Diluted CaCO ₃ slurry	☐	☐	-	SS2-044

In addition to the S2 coupons, a mirror-like S1 coupons (30x40x2 mm) and unpolished Ag925 coupon (30x30x0.6 mm) were used in the feasibility test of RTI. The mirror-like S1 coupon was aged with the same method for 10 h and therefore shows a strong tarnish appearance. The unpolished Ag925 coupon was aged in

⁴ The semi-polished surface finish refers to a surface level slightly lower than the mirror-like surface finish. Such semi-polished finish was processed by the manufacturer, therefore very fine rolling marks are present on the surface.

a previous project at He-Arc CR and appears lightly tarnished. The left part of this coupon was cleaned with the CaCO_3 slurry, and the right part remains uncleaned.

Methods

Conventional photo acquisition

The conventional photo acquisition included overall photos for the SS2 and SP2 coupon batches together and photos acquired for SS2 or SP2 coupon batches separately. The overall photos focused on the tarnished sides of the coupons. They were acquired with the camera mounted on a portable stative. The separate photos were acquired for both tarnished and cleaned sides of the coupons, using the reproduction table.

For comparison, conventional photos with and without the polarizer filter were also acquired for each single coupon of those measured with RTI, using the same camera settings for the acquisition inside of the dome.

RTI

A feasibility test was performed on the strongly tarnished mirror-like S1 coupon and the matte Ag925 coupon. The purpose of the strongly tarnished mirror-like S1 coupon was for observing the tarnish colour and homogeneity, while the matte Ag925 coupon was to verify if surface damages (e.g., scratches) caused by the cleaning materials can be observed by RTI. A total of 48 photos were taken of one coupon with the sequence from LED1 to LED48 inside of the dome. No polarizer filter was used. The photos were then incorporated in *Authentica Creator* software to create RTI images.

During the formal test, the tarnished sides of two SS2 (i.e., SS2-035, SS2-041) and two SP2 (i.e., SP2-035, SP2-041) were first processed with RTI, for observing the difference between the strong and light tarnish appearances, as well as the difference between SS2 and SP coupons. For comparison, conventional photos with and without the polarizer filter were also acquired, using the same camera settings for those photos taken inside of the dome.

The cleaned sides of four SS2 coupons (i.e., SS2-035, SS2-038, SS2-041 and SS2-044) and four SP2 coupons (i.e., SP2-035, SP2-038, SP2-041 and SP2-044), representing the sterling silver and pure silver surfaces cleaned with four benchmarks, were then processed with RTI with three different acquisition set-ups. The first acquisition was obtained with the total 48 LED lights; the second acquisition was with the LEDs 25 to 48 (lower range LEDs on the dome), taking two photos per LED for obtaining 48 photos. The lower ranges of LEDs used in the second acquisition are low-angle lights, which were expected to provide more details of the surface conditions. However, no scratching marks can be clearly observed with both first and second acquisitions. Therefore, the third acquisition with the LEDs 1 to 24 (upper range LEDs on the dome) was performed, taking two photos per LED for obtaining 48 photos. With this acquisition, scratches are observable in RTI images. It is worth noting that after the photo integration with the RTI software, some scratching marks appear less obvious than some individual photos that were taken under specific lighting angle inside of the dome.

3.4 Results of experiments with object/mock-ups

Conventional photo acquisition

Acquisition with the reproduction table

Figure 15 presents photos of the tarnished sides of six SS2 (a) and six SP2 (b) coupons that were aged with AS for 10 h, as well as the tarnished sides of six SS2 (c) and six SP2 (d) coupons that were aged with AS for 3 h. It is observed that both strongly tarnished SS2 and SP2 coupons appear dark grey to a similar extent. The lightly tarnished SS2 and SP2 coupons exhibit some colour nuances: The strongly tarnished coupons show a relatively more homogeneous and brownish appearance, while the lightly tarnished coupons appear more greyish and less homogeneous.

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Figure 15. Photos of tarnished silver coupons: (a) strongly tarnished SS2 coupons; (b) strongly tarnished SP2 coupons; (c) lightly tarnished SS2 coupons; (d) lightly tarnished SP2 coupons.

Conventional photos for the cleaned sides of the above-mentioned coupons, together with the unaged reference coupons (i.e., SS2-045, SP2-045) are presented in Figure 16. Unfortunately, no significant scratching marks can be observed in such photos taken with the conventional photo acquisition method and the reproducible table.

Figure 16. Photos of SS2 and SP2 coupons cleaned with selected benchmark methods.

Acquisition with the portable camera stative

The overall photos that were acquired with the portable camera stative are presented in Figure 17, including the photos with the two table lamps placed with some distance (ca. 1 m) (a, b) and those with the two table lamps placed very close to each other (lamp shades touching each other) (c, d). The photos taken with the table lamps with some distance all appear dark, while the photos taken with the lamps very close to each other show some colour differences. The latter despite a high intensity of the light reflection. It is observed that the strongly tarnished coupons show a more greyish colour tone (c) and the light tarnish appears more blueish surrounded with irregular grey edges. Compared to those photos acquired with the reproduction table, photos in Figure 17c, d show more details about the tarnish colour and homogeneity. A balance between the photos with the reproduction table and those with the portable stative is more compatible with the visual observation.

Figure 17. Photos of SS2-033 to SS2-038 (a) and SS2-039 and SS2-044 (b), obtained when the lamps had a fairly large distance; photos of SS2-033 to SS2-038 (c) and SS2-039 to SS2-044 (d), obtained when the lamps were close to each other.

Reflectance Transformation Imaging

Feasibility test

A comparison between the conventional photo and RTI images of the mirror-like SS1 coupon is presented in Figure 18. It is evident that RTI images (Figure 18b-f) show more details about the tarnish appearance such as tarnish colour and homogeneity than conventional photos (Figure 18a). Furthermore, RTI images obtained from different lighting angles can provide focused surface textures. Some polishing marks on the coupon surface can also be observed in RTI images.

Figure 18. (a) Conventional photo of an aged mirror-like SS1 coupon without the polarizer filter; (b-f) RTI images of the coupon created from different light directions: middle, left, right, up and down.

A second comparison between the conventional photo and RTI image of the unpolished Ag925 coupon is presented in Figure 19. A relatively large scratch formed in the cleaning process with the CaCO_3 slurry can be clearly seen in the RTI image (within the red frame), while in the conventional photo such scratch is not readily observable. Note that since the camera lens needs to be directly above the coupon during the photo acquisition inside of the dome, light reflection of the lens cannot be fully avoided. The RTI images of the cleaned side of the coupon thus appears darker (Figure 19b).

Figure 19. (a) Conventional photo of the lightly tarnished Ag925 coupon (b) RTI image of the coupon, with the light from the right lower angle.

RTI for silver coupons cleaned with benchmarks

Tarnished side of S2 coupons - RTI images of the tarnished sides of SS2-035, SS2-041, SP2-035 and SP2-041 are presented in Figure 20. It is observed that the strong tarnish (a, c) shows a more purplish colour tone, while the light tarnish (b, d) appears more brownish. Some colour differences between the SS2 and SP2 coupons can also be observed. Compared to the conventional photos with and without the polarizer filter, which show a more green-blueish colour tone, the RTI images are more compatible with visual observations and provide more details of surface features.

Figure 20. RTI images and conventional photos with/without the polarizer filter for the tarnished sides of SS2-035, SS2-041, SP2-035 and SP2-041.

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Cleaned side of S2 coupons - RTI images of the unaged reference coupons and the cleaned sides of the coupons cleaned with benchmarks are presented in Figure 21. Photos that were taken under LED12 inside of the dome are also included in the figure, for the purpose of comparison. The dark tone of the RTI images and the LED12 photos was due to the reflection of the lens, because the camera cannot be tilted during the photo acquisition inside of the dome, due to technical restriction of the mounting system. Note that the rolling marks are in the vertical direction, while the cleaning marks are in relatively horizontal directions. It is evident that the unaged reference coupons show much more homogenous surfaces than the cleaned coupons. Such inhomogeneous appearances of the latter indicate that the cleaning process with the benchmarks not only removed the tarnish layer, but also remove some base metal, leading to an uneven surface of the silver substrate. Of the cleaned coupons, the RTI image of SP2-044 appears slightly brownish, indicating the presence of some tarnish residues on the coupon surface, while the RTI images of the others do not show such brown tone. From the photos taken under LED12, it can be observed that SS2-041 and SP2-04, which were cleaned with the Hagerty polish cloth, show the most homogeneous cleaning appearances, followed by SS2-038 and SP2-038 that were cleaned with the Hagerty polish cream. Such observations indicate the commercial benchmarks seems to have better cleaning effects and leave less residues than the non-commercial ones. Note that except for SS2-041 and SP2-041 that were cleaned by rubbing the polish cloth on the coupon surface, the other coupons were all cleaned by swabbing with cotton sticks dipped with the slurries or cream. It seems that cotton swabbing can cause a relatively uneven surface, compared to rubbing with a cloth.

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Figure 21. RTI images and photos taken under LED12 for the reference coupons and the cleaned sides of four SS2 coupons (left part) and those of SP2 coupons (right part).

Figure 22 presents conventional photos with and without the polarizers filter for the coupons shown in Figure 21. No surface details are observed in these photos. There is no significant difference between the photos acquired with the filter and those without the filter, except for a slight colour difference (i.e., photos with the filter show a pale green tone), indicating that it is not the filter but the sample position (i.e., away from the lens) that plays the decisive role for avoiding the lens reflection.

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Figure 22. Conventional photos with and without the polarizer filter for the reference coupons and the cleaned sides of four SS2 coupons (left part) and those of four SP2 coupons (right part).

Comparison with Optical Microscopy

For the purpose of comparison, optical microscopy (OM) images in both bright field (BF) and dark field (DF) of the cleaned coupons are presented in Figure 23. The OM images show clearer scratches, compared to the RTI images, but they do not provide information about the cleaning homogeneity as RTI images. The thicker and darker rolling marks shown in the OM-BF images of SP2-035 and SP2-044, which were cleaned with the CaCO₃ slurry and its diluted version respectively, indicates that some tarnish residues are embedded in the rolling marks of these two coupons, which is compatible with the RTI image of SP2-044. The tarnish residue issues observed through both RTI and OM further suggests that the non-commercial benchmarks may not be efficient to remove the tarnish layer on the silver surfaces.

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Figure 23. OM images of the unaged reference coupons and coupons cleaned with benchmarks.

3.5 Test user-group feedback

Not applicable.

3.6 Summary of protocols

There is no significant difference between conventional photos acquired with and without the polarizer filter. To avoid the light reflection of the camera lens, it is more important to move the sample slightly away from the lens, rather than using the filter.

In terms of the tarnished sides of silver coupons, conventional photos can be acquired either with a portable camera stative or a reproduction table. For photos of coupon batches that consist of a limited quantity of coupons (e.g., 6 or 7 S2 coupons in our case), a reproduction table is recommended, due to the ease of lighting adjustment and higher reproducibility. Photos including more coupons (e.g., 12 S2 coupons) can be acquired with the portable stative, using two table lamps for lighting. When the table lamps are close to each other, some colour differences between the light tarnish and strong tarnish as well as those between SS2

and SP2 coupons can be observed in photos. However, such photos show strong light reflection, which may be possibly reduced by adjusting the lamp intensity. Compared to conventional photos, RTI images show tarnish colours closer to visual observations and provide more surface details.

For the cleaned sides of the coupons that are highly reflective due to the cleaning or polishing by the benchmarks, conventional photos are not able to show surface details or cleaning marks. Alternatively, RTI images can provide information about cleaning homogeneity and tarnish residues. Therefore, RTI images can be used as supportive data for the assessment of cleaning efficacy of benchmarks. Oblivious scratching marks can be observed from the photos acquired under certain LEDs inside of the dome. Based on the results of RTI and OM observations, it is concluded that the commercial benchmarks (i.e. Hagerty polish cream and Hagerty polish cloth used in this project) are more efficient for removing both strong and light tarnish, compared to the non-commercial methods (i.e., the CaCO₃ slurry and its diluted version).

In general, acquisition of conventional photos for a batch of coupons with highly reflective surfaces e.g., cleaned silver coupons, require continuous adjustments for both camera and light settings and is thus time consuming. On the contrary, the photo acquisition part in RTI is simple and easy to handle, but the request of a total 48 photos for RTI processing can be an issue in terms of digital sobriety and time cost, especially when continuous fine adjustments for the sample height and camera settings are needed: the adjustment result of each time can only be observed after 48 photos are acquired and processed.

A summary of the imaging protocols developed in this project is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Protocols developed in the project for imaging of metal surfaces.

Imaging technique	Targeted objects	Camera support	Support settings	Camera equipment	Camera settings	Limitation	Acquisition effects
Conventional photo	Batches of untarnished silver coupons with matte surface / batches of tarnished silver coupon with polished surface.	Reproduction table mounted with 2 lamps.	Camera height of 23 cm, lamp height of level 4, lamp angle of ca. 22°, lamps facing towards each other.	Canon 600D, Canon 18-55 mm objective, with Dörr circular polarizer filter.	1/30 s, f9, ISO100, 5200k	Limited coupon quantity.	Closer to visual observation.
		Portable camera stative with 2 table lamps.	Table lamps placed with some distance or close to each other.	Canon 600D, Canon 18-55 mm objective, with Dörr circular polarizer filter.	Lamps placed with distance: 1/20 s, f8, ISO100, 5200k Lamps placed close: 1/60 s, f11, ISO100, 5200k	Limited light settings.	Lamps placed with distance: appear all dark. Lamps placed close: colour nuances btw tarnish types & btw coupon types observed, but with strong light reflection.
	Batches of unaged/cleaned silver coupons with highly polished surface.	Reproduction table mounted with 2 lamps.	Camera height of 23 cm, lamp height of level 6.	Canon 600D, Canon 18-55 mm objective, with Dörr circular polarizer filter.	1/60 s, f11, ISO100, 5200k	Limited coupon quantity.	No lens reflection, no surface details.
	Single unaged/cleaned silver coupons with highly polished surface.	Reproduction table & portable camera stative.	Table lamps placed close to each other.	Canon 700D, Canon 60 mm objective, with/out Dörr circular polarizer filter.	1/50 s, f7.1, ISO200, 5200k	Single coupon.	
RTI	Single tarnished and cleaned sides of silver coupons with highly polished	Broncolor Scope D50 dome mounted with 48 LEDs.	Sample stage height of 11 cm.	Canon 700D, Canon 60 mm objective, with Dörr circular polarizer filter.	1/50 s, f7.1, ISO200, 5200k	48 photos requested, processing only with <i>Authentic</i>	more correct tarnish colours, details of surface features.

	surface.					<i>a Creator</i> software.	
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3.7 Protocol limitations and advances

The conventional photo acquisitions in this project were based on simple equipment currently available at HE-Arc CR. The set-ups for lighting and camera were restricted to small-sized coupons with a flat and smooth surface. To avoid light reflection of the camera lens, the camera needs to be tilted by ca. 5° and the sample needs to be slightly away from the lens, which may lead to uneven lighting conditions. To overcome this problem, a tilt-shift lens is recommended.

The photo acquisition inside of the dome has specific requests for the camera position and the working distance between the sample and lens. For example, the front of the lens needs to be slightly above the upper opening of the dome but cannot be larger than 5 cm. The maximum distance between the sample and camera lens is 20 cm. Such specifications restrict the sample size suitable for RTI. Also, the RTI software *Authentica Creator* was designed and produced by the same company that produced the *Broncolor Scope D50* dome. A free user license is restricted to two logins, with the purchase of the dome. Some free RTI software such as *RTIBuilder* and *RTIViewer* can be downloaded from the website of Cultural Heritage Imaging (www.culturalheritageimaging.org), and they provide more advanced imaging functions.

A RTI dome is rather costly. However, it is possible to construct a simple RTI dome with less expensive and easily accessible materials and equipment and making use of open-source software. For example, a customized RTI dome was built by the porcelain workshop in the Rijksmuseum (Figure 24).⁵ One small dome to use with the Dinolite and the other is the large dome with a regular camera.

Figure 24. Self-built RTI system with a small dome using a Dinolite (left) and a larger dome using a regular camera (right). Photo's: Julia Wagner (student of the programme: Advanced Professional Programme of Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage, Glass and Ceramics, at the University of Amsterdam, 2020/2021).

For observing micro-scale surface features, a micro-RTI is recommended (Siato 2023). Recently, a portable RTI instrument, named *MorphoLight*, has been developed for surface characterization. Using a topographical analysis method, which improves the surface gradient characterization, slope/curvature maps of objects can be analysed (Lemesle and Bigerelle 2024), which could be useful for investigating metal objects that often contain curved surfaces.

⁵ <https://allardpierson.nl/blog/documenting-physical-evidence-of-roman-glass-making-processes/>

3.8 Conclusion and next steps

RTI provides surface details that are not readily observable in conventional photos, therefore this technique can be useful for investigating possible etching effect of base metal by certain cleaning methods/materials. For example, a deep eutectic solvent (DES) prepared with choline chloride and ascorbic acid at a molar ratio of 2:1 is reported to be suitable for a selective cleaning of malachite-like corrosion products on copper objects (Tsurumaki et al. 2022). However, during our tests on aged copper and brass coupons, it was observed that the cleaning by this DES occurred very fast (within 1 min) and the cleaned brass coupons appeared pinkish, indicating leaching of the element zinc. Since such DES has a strong acidic pH (ca. 1), it was suspected that it may etch the base metal while removing the corrosion products. Unfortunately, OM images did not provide useful information and SEM imaging has a rather limited observation view (experiments not performed yet). It is expected that RTI will provide useful information about whether the metal base was etched or not. The RTI images obtained from the silver coupons cleaned with benchmarks will be used as references in the next stage of metal cleaning in GoGreen, for the assessment of cleaning efficacy of the historical treatments and innovative green methods.

Most historical silver objects exhibit abundant beautiful surface features, which resulted from surface decoration techniques such as Repoussé, chasing, relief and engraving that were extensively employed in the production of silverwares in history. In addition to surface decorations, silver trademarks that were often applied by hammering or punching indicate information regarding the silver purity, manufacturer or silversmith, sometimes the production date and some other additional information, and are therefore important tracking records and of high historical values. Such beautiful or important surface features should not be damaged or significantly reduced during the cleaning process, which is an important criterium for the assessment of cleaning methods. Due to the strong light reflection of silver surfaces after cleaning, especially with the abrasive methods, conventional photographs are not able to demonstrate the actual states of such surface features. Since RTI has the function of enhancing surface details, it is expected that RTI will provide important supportive evidence for the assessment of the cleaning of selected silver case studies, which will be performed at a more advanced stage of the project. By comparison between RTI images before and after cleaning, possible damage or significant reduction of the surface features should be clearly observed.

In this project, green and sustainability considerations have been integrated into several components across various stages. For instance, the artificial tarnishing of the silver coupons was performed with the albumin solution method, which is a green aging method developed in the GoGreen project. During the aging process, hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) vapor was gradually emitted from the pure egg white albumin solution with the aid of heat and interacted with the silver surface to produce tarnishing product. Compared to chemical aging methods that are commonly used in the conservation field, such aging materials are non-toxic, bio-degradable, no harm to operators, eco-friendly, and less costly than chemical compounds used for the silver aging. Furthermore, the instruments, devices and materials used in the project are mainly reusable or reproducible. For example, as described with the name “reproduction table”, technical parameters regarding the camera mounting and light settings during the photograph acquisition of the coupons can be recorded by marking heights and/or angles on the camera holder and light holders, which makes the photo acquisition of same type of coupons reproducible and saves a great amount of time for the re-adjustment of technical settings. The black Canson paper that functioned as the background during RTI acquisition has also been repeated used. Before the acquisition of each coupon, possible residues of tarnishing products on the paper were removed with fine brushing.

It is worth noting that following the fast development of RTI data processing techniques, the application of RTI will show very promising future in the field of heritage research. Over the past decade the range of algorithms in the broad domain of RTI has greatly increased, addressing issues such as large resolution capture, 3D RTI, annotation, etc. (Earl et al. 2011). For example, RTI has been used in the process of

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digitalization of stamps on Greek amphorae that have been recently excavations at ancient Tanais, Russia (Lech et al. 2021). Reconstruction of 3D profiles of archaeological objects can be made by applying the technique of photometric stereo imaging to the RTI images (Florindi et al. 2020).

4. LSI

4.1 Concept

In cultural heritage, damage prevention begins with monitoring an object's physical and chemical properties, both during display and remedial treatments like cleaning. Quick diagnosis supports treatment decisions, but visual inspection may miss early-stage damage. While experts with advanced equipment can assess an object's state, this can be time-consuming. A passive, non-invasive, and quantitative monitoring method would save time. Non-invasive monitoring tools employed for monitoring in cultural heritage nowadays are for example acoustic emission, handheld FTIR, strain gauges for wood, photogrammetry et cetera. These non-invasive monitoring tools are unable to monitor internal dynamics of a heterogeneous opaque object on different length- and timescales, but laser speckle imaging can. Therefore, we propose laser speckle imaging (LSI) as a relatively new, portable, accessible monitoring tool for cultural heritage objects. This technique uses interference to create a speckle pattern. A few years ago, earlier work (Buijs et al, 2019; Baij et al, 2020) has shown that laser speckle imaging is powerful for visualizing microscopic motion in real-time using an efficient Fast Fourier Transform to quantify speckle fluctuations by converting its fluctuations to the frequency domain without loss of quantitative information (Wiener-Kinchin theorem). For more detailed information about the underlying mathematical principles behind the laser speckle imaging apparatus, the reader is referred to Buijs et al, 2019.

In principle, a power spectrum is obtained from a Fourier Transform of the measured autocorrelation function. The rate of speckle pattern fluctuation, i.e. the temporal fluctuation, is characterized by its distinct frequencies. The power spectrum shows the distribution of observed power among different frequencies. This is useful, because those distinct frequencies can be used to monitor and distinguish different internal dynamics in opaque cultural heritage objects using LSI. In our work we have used LSI to monitor the effect of different cleaning methods on the internal dynamics of a paint, later referred as solvent-induced dynamics. Using this approach, we have been able to determine how long the solvent was inside the painting and how far the solvent spread during application of the tissue. The solvent retention and exposure time are preferably minimized during varnish removal in order to reduce solvent-induced chemical degradation reactions inside the painting.

We used a portable LSI set-up made by the start-up NanoMoi. This work also highlights the operability of this device using its user-friendly software and its technical considerations when measuring an object. This technique can also be used to monitor other physical processes like crack development. The advantage of this technique is that the software and data-collection techniques are optimized for the conservator and so they can assess the dynamics of an object in real-time without advanced post-analysis. This makes the technique accessible for conservators.

In our studies, one of our goals was to determine whether green solvents can be a suitable alternative for conventional non-green solvents for varnish removal. Therefore, we also used ethanol, gamma-valerolactone (GVL) and dimethyl carbonate (DMC), beside the traditionally used solvents. These solvents can be obtained by a sustainable synthesis route. Ethanol, although toxic, is derived from carbohydrates and can be produced from carbohydrate-containing feedstocks through fermentation. GVL is derived from renewable lignocellulosic biomass and dimethyl carbonate can even be produced from CO₂ using new alternative production processes.

4.2 Experimental Set-up

The experimental set-up is depicted in 25. The samples were illuminated by a 520 nm laser at 20 mW. The laser beam was diverged to a broad illumination beam before it exited the instrument case using a diverging lens. The instrument has two camera's: a monochrome camera was used to capture reflected light to generate and analyse speckle patterns and a RGB camera was used to capture a live color view of the working area. Both

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cameras are well aligned to the same area. The instrument achieved a 3 x 4 cm imaging area at approximately 70 cm working distance. A ring light was used to uniformly illuminate the area. The internal dynamics were quantified by Fourier transform analysis in real-time, by software developed by Buijs *et al* and transformed into false-colour images. The LSI instrument and software used in this project were developed by the company NanoMoi.

Figure 25. The experimental set-up of the laser speckle imaging device (left) and a schematic diagram (right).

Technical parameters

The provided software is intuitive and consists of different tabs. A control panel is available for checking the camera settings based on lightning and focus (Appendix VI). The lightning and focus can be changed by manually adjusting the aperture and focus of the camera using the focusing rings on both camera lenses. Via the software parameters, like the exposure time, the gain, the framerate, can be used to optimize measured signal (Appendix VI). Each parameter is further defined in Table 6. The FT-LSI parameter can be further refined during the measurement. These main parameters are FT-LSI length, filter-size and averaging of signal. The file saving parameters can also be further refined i.e. the time-interval, measurement time, raw data saving and saving of images. The settings on the software are for each measurement logged in a separate text file ('settings.txt'). To effectively utilize the laser speckle imaging device produced by NanoMoi, a general reference guide was also included in this section (Table 7). The reference guide only served as indication for a specific type of material. Commonly, the optimal settings can be found using trial-and-error. For optimization of choosing the right frequency for imaging, a spectrogram can help.

Table 6. Technical parameters for laser speckle imaging.

Parameter	Explanation
Exposure time (T)	Length of time the sensor of the camera is exposed to light. The greater the exposure time, the more light is going to the detector. Under- and over-exposure both decrease the dynamic range of the camera and the sensitivity of the instrument.
Gain (dB)	Represents the amplification of a signal. The following formula is used for determining the amplification of the signal: $\text{gain (dB)} = 10 \log_{10} (P_{\text{out}}/P_{\text{in}}).$ P_{out} is the output of the camera P_{in} is the signal input
Framerate	The rate of picture collection during the measurements, expressed as images per

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(fps)	second (fps). Faster motions can be collected by increasing the framerate.
FT-LSI length	The length of the timeseries (images) used to calculate one LSI image. Slower motion can be captured by increasing the FT-LSI length.
Filter-size	The filter-size is a spatial filter of the signal. It determines the N x N pixel size (input = N) to which the Fourier Transform is applied. The computation time and spatial resolution decreases with increasing filter-size.
Region of interest mapping	Self-explanatory. The average power density is calculated from the region of interest and the calculated LSI-images are recorded.
Averaging	Number of frames to average in order to increase statistics in time. However, this reduces the time-resolution of the measurement.
Frequency imaging	The frequency of motion is chosen to image during the measurement. Commonly, the frequency of motion is determined with the aid of a spectrogram (see next section).

Table 7. Reference guide for FT-LSI experimental settings.

Parameter	Object color		Motion	
	Dark (brown, red, black)	Light (white, yellow)	Slow	Fast
Exposure time (T)	Long	Short	NA	NA
Gain (dB)	High	Low	High	Low
Framerate (fps)	NA	NA	Slow	Slow
FT-LSI length	Long	Long	Short	Short
Filter-size	NA	NA	NA	NA
Region of interest mapping	NA	NA	NA	NA
Averaging	More	More	More	Less
Frequency imaging	NA	NA	Slow	Slow

Spectrogram and time traces

A spectrogram shows the spectrum of frequencies of a signal during the measurement time, often displayed as heatmap. As the signal can vary over time, the spectrogram can identify a change in power of a frequency which may represent a change in internal dynamics. Therefore, the spectrogram can be useful to determine an optimal frequency for frequency imaging representing a process of interest. Due to calculation time, obtaining a spectrogram and simultaneously performing frequency imaging is not possible. An example of a spectrogram is provided in Figure 26, which comes from a measurement in which a varnish layer was removed with a tissue loaded with solvent. Figure 26a illustrates the background before the cleaning of the oil paint. The spectrogram shows a constant signal. Between 0 and 1 Hz, the signal showed a constant higher power than the power of frequencies above 1 Hz. When removing the varnish from the paint (Figure 26B), the power at every frequency increased as indicated by a more yellow color. The power increase was greatest at frequencies below 1 Hz. Later, the power declined for each frequency. This was a consequence of decreased solvent-induced dynamics in the painting. The amount of solvent in the painting decreased with increasing exposure time. From this spectrogram we derived that frequency imaging below 1 Hz is more useful. The signal-to-background is greater than at frequencies above 1 Hz despite a greater background power at frequencies below 1 Hz.

Figure 26. (A) Background spectrogram measured before cleaning of an oil paint. (B) Spectrogram taken after varnish and corresponding tissue removal. (C) After twenty minutes of varnish removal and removal of the tissue.

4.3 Methodological Approach

Oil paint films were prepared with a thin varnish top-layer. Those mock-ups were placed under the LSI set-up with a distance between the instrument case and the mock-up of approximately 70 cm. Within the area of 3 x 4 cm, a rectangular area was selected as the region of interest (ROI, details see Appendix VIIA). The solvent carrier was loaded with the desired solvent and then attached to the region of interest for a certain amount of time (see next sections). The activity was measured using FT-LSI at a specific time interval (Appendix VIIA). The varnish removal experiments with tissue were done in a lighted room. Later, varnish removal experiments with a cotton swab were measured in a dark room to avoid additional effects of light on the measurement. Frequency imaging was performed at a single frequency to visualize the power of the solvent-induced dynamics for every pixel at each timepoint (Appendix VIIA). The corresponding decaying time traces (or frequency bins) of the ROI were saved. The FT-LSI measurements were run for 20 to 30 minutes depending on the specific experiment. The images were initially examined using ImageJ and later the time traces were further examined.

4.4 Description of the object/mock-ups

Mock-ups

The cleaning tests will be performed on different paint mock-ups. There are three types of mock-ups: i) paint on glass samples, (Figure 27). The paint on glass samples were prepared at the University of Amsterdam, Netherlands. The paint layer was made by grinding the white zinc oxide pigments with cold-pressed untreated linseed oil in a 1:1 (w/w) ratio to a smooth paste with mortar and pestle. This mixture was spread onto 75 x 50 mm glass slides by using a draw-down bar. With the help of extra glass slides and tapes, the draw-down bar was elevated to achieve a homogeneous paint layer of around 190 μm wet thickness. The samples were later put into an oven and cured in the dark at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 7 days without controlling the humidity.

Figure 27. One of the glass samples was under visible light.

Varnish preparation

The 25% dammar varnish by weight was prepared in Shellsol A and Shellsol T solvents. The samples were fixed on a whiteboard with double-sided tape, and varnish was applied with a brush. The entire surface of the glass slides was coated with dammar varnish (Figure 28). After the layer dried, the applications were repeated 5 times. They were put into the UV ageing chamber for 7 days under UV-A and UV-B radiation (Figure 29). The total radiation dosage was $1.4 \times 10^7 \text{ J/cm}^2$ (UV-A) and $5.2 \times 10^7 \text{ J/cm}^2$ (UV-B). The total thickness of the paint samples with varnish after ageing is around $120 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 28. The varnish solution (left) and the samples under varnish (right).

Figure 29. The UV ageing chamber (left) and some samples after ageing (right).

Preparation of tissues

Evolon® CR tissue and solvent pre-loaded Evolon CR was provided by the Restauratieatelier, Rijksmuseum. Before the application, the Evolon® CR tissue was pre-washed to avoid the release of unwanted saturated fatty acids into the paint and metal soap formation. The tissue was washed with water three times and repeated the same procedure with excess acetone. The tissue preparation steps were followed as described in Tauber et al, 2018. The solvent loading was determined with equation 1.

$$m_{solvent} = m_{Evolon} \times 3,8 \times \frac{loadingpercentage}{100\%} \quad (1)$$

After the preparations, the tissue was cut into desired size (0.7 x 0.7 cm). The solvent was then added through a pipette, and they were stored in sealed vials one day before application to prevent solvent evaporation in the surroundings and achieve a homogeneous distribution of solvent throughout the tissue.

Electrospun PA 6,6 material

The electrospun polyamide PA 6,6 used in this research was produced at the University of Bologna, Italy, provided by and described in Ramacciotti, 2023 (Figure 30). Polyamide was dissolved in HFIP (Hexafluoro-2-propanol) at 10% concentrations and stirred until all the polymer dissolved at room temperature. The small pore PA 6,6 has a fibre diameter of around 0.5 µm. After the tissue was cut into small squares, they were weighted, and the solvent amount was calculated following the fixed ratio: 9 microliters per milligram for 100% solvent loading, and 3.96 microliters per milligram for 44% solvent loading.

Figure 30. The electrospun PA 6,6 tissue was used in the experiment.

Cleaning tests

The cleaning tests were carried out with different application times and application methods – with coverslip to press the tissue in case of testing the tissues. The size of the tissues was 0.7 x 0.7 cm squares. 44% of solvent loading for Evolon® CR tissues and 100% solvent loading for PA 6,6 were tested. The application times were thirty seconds, one minute and five minutes respectively. The FT-LSI captured the solvent induced motion using provided settings (see appendices for both experiments). For the cleaning benchmark workshop, a cotton swab was used for the different experiments for either 10 or 15 seconds of application time depending on the solvent and painting type.

Cleaning benchmark workshop

The reader is referred to GoGreen Deliverable D3.2 for further information about this workshop. For this study, we have used a selection of paints and corresponding varnishes and solvents. Cotton swabs were used and loaded with different solvents in order to remove the varnish.

4.5 Results of experiments with object/mock-ups

Time trace analysis

The effects of varnish removal from a zinc white linseed oil based paint (thickness ~ 120 µm) with dammar was investigated. The influence of application time, solvent and tissue type on the removal of varnish on a zinc white oil paint and the solvent retention time was studied. The experimental settings for each experiment can be found in the appendix as well as the tested tissues and solvents (Appendix VIIB). This work demonstrated the potential of LSI to assess the solvent retention time under various conditions. An example of a typical time trace of the experiment is shown (Figure 31). The other recorded time traces are attached in Appendix VIIB. An overview of the results is depicted in Figure 31b. The calculation of t_{75} was influenced by the measured motion which was induced by the removal of tissue. For this reason, an inaccurate reference point existed for varnish removal with tissues. In addition, the solvent may evaporate during longer application times or may still be present after the measurement since the time traces were sometimes still showing a decay at the end of the measurement. Nevertheless, the following trends were observed:

Application time. The longer the application time, the longer the solvent remained inside the painting.

Tissue type. The solvent remained longer in the painting when PA 6,6 tissue was used instead of Evolon® CR. However, the solvent loading was respectively 100 vs. 44 % of its solvent capacity. PA 6,6 is known for a slower

solvent release rate than Evolon® CR (Rammacciotti et al., 2024), but the solvent retention was still more for PA 6,6 than for Evolon® CR probably due its solvent loadings.

Solvent. The order of measured solvent retention for the different combinations of tissue and solvents were summarized (see below). The solvent retention time is a result of solvent penetration, solvent release rate from the tissue and solvent evaporation. Therefore, the cause for the solvent retention was not precisely unknown. FT-LSI only distinguished how long a solvent remain inside the painting for the different combinations of tissue, application time and solvent.

PA 6,6:

t = 30 and 60 s: $t_{75_{ethanol}} < t_{75_{acetone}} < t_{75_{DMC}} < t_{75_{GVL}}$

t = 5 min: $t_{75_{DMC}} < t_{75_{ethanol}} < t_{75_{acetone}} < t_{75_{GVL}}$

Evolon® CR:

t = 30 and 60 s: $t_{75_{GVL}} < t_{75_{ethanol}} < t_{75_{DMC}} < t_{75_{acetone}}$

t = 5 min: $t_{75_{acetone}} < t_{75_{GVL}} < t_{75_{DMC}}$. Ethanol evaporated during the varnish removal with Evolon® CR with an application time of five minutes.

Figure 31. (A) The time trace during- and after removal of Evolon® CR tissue loaded with 44% acetone on a zinc white oil paint varnished with dammar. (B) Overview of solvent retention of different solvents loaded with various solvents. The triangles represent PA 6,6 tissue and the circles represent Evolon® CR. Group 1, 2 and 3 represent application times of 30, 60 and 300 seconds respectively.

Frequency imaging

During application of the tissue

The application of the tissue on the painting was also recorded with FT-LSI when the tissue was still positioned on the painting. This is useful to determine whether the solvent unwantedly spread out during the application of tissue on the varnish. An example is shown in Figure 32 in which the solvent was spread on the paint outside the location on which the Evolon® CR was originally applied. In addition, we can also see that the activity is heterogeneously distributed. The left part of the tissue showed more activity than its right part. We summarized the fact that solvent spread out during application in Table 8 and added supporting information (Appendix VIIC). We found that tissues with acetone and ethanol showed solvent spreading during application, while GVL and DMC showed no observable solvent spreading during application. In addition, PA 6,6 showed less solvent spreading than the Evolon® CR tissue, likely due to a higher solvent amount since PA 6,6 was fully saturated. In this work, we only used FT-LSI to visualize the solvent spreading during application. However, the

cause for this spreading in this work is ambiguous. It may be the solvent absorption capacity for the different solvents was different although this was not tested for these Evolon® CR sheets. The viscosity of the solvents could have also caused additional spreading since the viscosities of ethanol and acetone were smaller than GVL and DMC.

Evolon, acetone, $t = 60$ s

Figure 32. Frequency imaging (1.6 Hz) of Evolon® CR loaded with 44% acetone (60 seconds) on a zinc white paint varnished with dammar. The area of the Evolon® tissue is indicated with the red square.

Table 8. Overview of the solvent spreading with different combinations of solvent and tissue.

Tissue	Solvent	Solvent spreading
Evolon (44% loading)	Ethanol	✓
	Acetone	✓
	GVL	-
	DMC	-
PA 6,6 (100% loading)	Ethanol	✓
	Acetone	✓
	GVL	-
	DMC	-

During varnish removal

Frequency imaging was also useful for determining any solvent spreading across the surface after application. In addition, other phenomena like the evaporation of solvent may be found. An example of FT-LSI images after application with Evolon® CR with acetone was depicted in Figure 33. Expectedly and in accordance with previous section, we again found that this combination of tissue and application time also resulted in solvent spreading after application of the tissue. In addition, the resulted solvent-induced motion decreased at longer times in accordance with the lifetime traces. In addition to the above, we also found that PA 6,6 with DMC showed appearing and disappearing intense circles. These circles might indicate that the solvent was evaporating after removal of the tissue (Figure 34).

Evolon, acetone, $t = 60$ s

Figure 33. Frequency imaging (1.6 Hz) during ($t < 60$ s) and after ($t > 60$ s) the application of Evolon® CR loaded with acetone (44%) on a zinc white paint varnished with dammar.

PA 6,6, DMC, $t = 60$ s

Figure 34. Frequency imaging (1.6 Hz) after the application of PA 6,6 loaded with DMC (100%) on a zinc white paint varnished with dammar (250 – 600 s). The blue arrows indicate increased temporal activity.

Time traces

The time traces of the different combinations for the low frequency bin were depicted in Figure 35. The solvent retention for the different paints were in close proximity to each other. Between the paints, it was found that a burnt sienna painting (Figure 35a) which was dark brown, showed a fast decay curve. The settings were adjusted with increased gain and exposure times but still the measured power was little. The start of the measured signal likely showed the influence of the cotton swab on the power, because the signal composes of the lag-time and the FT-LSI length. However, gain was also increased leading to increased noise levels making differentiation between the different solvent retention behaviors more difficult. Since the measured decay curves were in close proximity to each other and also noise was present, it was not possible to reliably determine a solvent retention time (t_{75}) to distinguish between the different solvent retention times. Nevertheless, we might have found that solvent retention of acetone in a Ruben's and sea landscape painting were shorter than the solvent retention of ethanol in both paintings. In general, this work showed that the solvent was almost completely gone at the surface after 20 minutes for all measured treatments. In this part, the frequency imaging was not reviewed because the cotton swab was used in a consistent way in every measurement with almost equal exposure times on a small contact area.

Figure 35. Measured time traces (low frequency bin: 0 – 1.25 Hz) after cotton swab removal loaded with solvent on a burnt sienna, sea landscape, Ruben's, zinc white varnished with either dammar or laropal painting (respectively A – E).

Cleaning benchmark workshop

In GoGreen deliverable D3.2 a survey was conducted with conservators removing various varnishes from different paints. In this study, FT-LSI was employed to assess solvent retention in various varnishes and paints subjected to different varnish removal techniques. For more information, see D3.2.

4.6 Test user-group feedback

The LSI was applied during the GoGreen cleaning benchmark workshop (11-14 June 2024, Amsterdam, see D3.2). The conservators found the technique useful for measuring the solvent-induced dynamics in real-time without complicated post-analysis. The technique was, according to the conservators, visible and easy to

implement. This technique would be accessible to the conservators. However, conservators indicated that the LSI measurements did not accurately reflect standard practice, as the cotton swab was held stationary on the painting rather than rolled multiple times as typically performed. It is important to note that this approach was employed to minimize human-induced variability, such as inconsistencies in rolling during repeated experiments. For future applications, involving a larger group of test users would provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the technique in diverse conservation scenarios.

4.7 Summary of LSI applications

We showed how FT-LSI can be used as a technique for evaluating the solvent retention inside a painting. This also leads to the opportunity to test the usefulness of FT-LSI in preliminary research in Operation Night Watch. In the introduction, it was mentioned that FT-LSI can be used to also monitor changes of surfaces. The measurable surface changes for FT-LSI includes the formation or growth of cracks because the speckle pattern will change as result of those changes. Preliminary research already showed how stress corrosion cracking (SCC) can be visually monitored in brass and silver plates using FT-LSI (Figure 36a). Secondly, FT-LSI may also be used to visually examine the success of consolidation on an object. For example, the success of glass consolidation may be verified using FT-LSI. Glass is transparent which offered the possibility to not only examine the surface, but also show in real-time how a transparent consolidant moves into the glass which is heavily crizzled or delaminated. A proof of concept was earlier captured with FT-LSI and is shown in Figure 36b⁶. As an outlook, the effectiveness of the treatment can be further assessed using FT-LSI by applying a solvent and analyzing whether the solvent exhibits the same transport patterns during FT-LSI frequency imaging. Additionally, attempts were made to measure changes in corroded metal under two different humidity conditions, but no significant results were observed within a two-week period.

⁶The investigation of solvent transport in heavily crizzled glass, initially captured using an earlier FT-LSI setup, forms part of preliminary research. Ongoing efforts are being made to replicate these results in heavily crizzled glass using the portable FT-LSI system in the GoGreen consortium.

Figure 36. Preliminary research. (A) Corrosion and SCC on metal surfaces captured with LSI. Above: images of corrosion ($d_2(\tau=6,000\text{ s})$) taken at 162000, 192000 and 234000 s, below: images of SCC ($d_2(\tau=200\text{ s})$) taken at 3402, 5442 and 8842 s. These sequences have the same scaling. (B) Snapshot of preliminary research in which a droplet of ethanol was put on heavily crizzled glass.

4.8 Protocol limitations and advances

The current FT-LSI set-up is useful to evaluate the response of an object during remedial treatments or during display with periodic monitoring. However, using FT-LSI has its limitations. For example, the FT-LSI is sensitive for external vibrations like the closing of a door. Therefore, the FT-LSI is preferably performed at a vibration-free environment or be located at a non-vibrating table. The sensitivity of FT-LSI can cause additional difficulty in data-interpretation because subtle differences might either exist because of changing background effects or true changes in the object. This can be in the future eliminated using a time-resolved background correction i.e. imaging two region of interests during the measurements. Next, the interpretation of FT-LSI results can be ambiguous. Although an autocorrelation between speckles and measured signal can hint towards a correlation, the cause for the potential correlation is unknown beforehand and therefore data-interpretation requires good understanding of the materials to determine the (likely) cause for those speckle pattern changes. As observed with the cleaning benchmark workshop it was also observed that the measurement of a burnt sienna painting, due its dark brown color, showed less signal than other paintings. Furthermore, the color differences of the objects causes that comparisons between objects can only be done qualitatively but not quantitatively i.e. compare the absolute measured values for the different objects.

In terms of advances, LSI was slow and qualitative. With the increase of computational power, modern LSI makes it possible to quantify motion using LSI. Until a few years ago, LSI was only a technique used by experts. The collection of data was simple, but data-processing was labor-intensive. There was a strong need for real-time monitoring using FT-LSI and standardization of the image-processing. NanoMoi made a portable LSI set-up with associated software to overcome both problems. With this package it was possible to monitor an object in real-time as showcased with measuring the solvent-induced motion inside a paint film. However, standardization and real-time monitoring has its associated disadvantages. With this set-up, it is not possible to reconstruct frequency images. The majority of the captured speckle images are removed to decrease storage space use and increase calculation times. As a result, the information obtained with this setup is limited in detail. Therefore, conservators must predetermine the specific frequency ranges they wish to measure using this approach. Conversely, as LSI continues to develop as a diagnostic tool for certain standard conservation practices, experimental parameters can be optimized for those specific procedures. Further refinement is required for other conservation treatments to extend the applicability of LSI to a broader range of interventions.

4.9 Conclusion and next steps

In this project, it was confirmed that FT-LSI can be used as determining both the solvent spreading and the time a solvent remained inside the painting. This was useful for determining the solvent retention time inside the painting which can aid, supplementary to analyzing the varnish removal efficiency of chosen method, the optimal varnish removal method. For now zinc white with dammar varnish was studied using the FT-LSI set-up. It would also be interesting to study other combinations of substrate, paint, varnish and application methods. For the cleaning benchmark workshop, FT-LSI was again useful for determining how long a solvent can approximately be inside different paintings when either Laropal or dammar varnishes were removed. The color of the paintings influenced the experimental settings as illustrated by a burnt sienna painting and hence the obtained signal. It cannot be excluded that the solvent retention was much shorter in a burnt sienna painting but it seems unlikely. From this and previous experiment, it showed FT-LSI can be used as a technique to study other real-life paintings and validate the solvent retention inside the painting during varnish removal. Now, this analytical technique was also recently introduced for the first time in Operation Night Watch, a research project aimed to preserve Rembrandt's painting *The Night Watch*, to evaluate the solvent retention during the removal of varnish.

FT-LSI is a promising low-tech technique for cultural heritage. It is relatively simple to use, cost-effective and the software is developed to store the optimal amount of photo's in line with the digital sobriety principles. As shown with two demonstrations, FT-LSI is already useful for capturing the solvent-induced dynamics during varnish removal on a variety of paintings, varnishes and application methods. Therefore, the use of FT-LSI can be further extended. This is for example done by preliminary research in Operation Night Watch. As mentioned, FT-LSI faces issues with its high sensitivity and non-specificity. The high sensitivity makes it for example prone to vibrations and airflow resulting in changes in measured signal, but on the other hand this sensitivity allows to detect micromotion like crack development and solvent-induced dynamics. In addition, the speckle pattern can be analyzed, but the explanation for speckle pattern changes requires material-specific expertise. As discussed in the outlook, the FT-LSI portable setup may be used for other surface examinations for example glass consolidation and monitoring crack development

In principle this analytical technique is developed by NanoMoi and can already be used in the conservation studio. The experiments suffered from a changing background for detecting subtle changes, especially at dark surfaces and using a high amplification of the signal. This can be partially overcome measuring a background area and a region of interest simultaneously. For other applications, it is recommended to first capture with the FT-LSI test-objects in which known change can be observed before using the FT-LSI to real-life objects. The cause for the LSI time traces could be ambiguous and expertise in the

material of choice is required for data-interpretation. In our preliminary study it was for example found that visualizing the transport of a solvent in heavily crizzled glass was not successful yet, but the visualization of solvent-induced motion during varnish removal was successful.⁷

In the future, the FT-LSI can become a more conventional technique for the cultural heritage field. With the growing number of active users, there are possibilities to build databases for standardized tests since all parameters should be the same for those tests. From these obtained databases, a comparative judgement can be made by the conservator or by the software itself. However, it also poses important questions on future documentation and data-storage. For example, the obtained videos and images are large and cannot all be stored. Then, the value of documentation must be reevaluated. Should FT-LSI serve as a tool for only fast, undocumented checks in the conservation studio? Or should we incorporate obtained videos and images as part of the documentation protocol? There are many data storage options available. Since this technology is at the beginning stages of application, we prioritized the added value of using this technology for different cultural heritage objects rather than large scale adoption. Nevertheless, these raised challenges are important to take into account as technology advances.

5. Deviations from the Description of the Action (if applicable)

Not applicable.

6. Conclusions

In summary, the findings from the various projects underscore the utility and limitations of different diagnostic techniques in the field of art conservation. Project 1 demonstrated that monochromatic filters offer limited practical advantages for assessing UV-induced photoluminescence in varnishes. However, these filters can enhance visibility in specific contexts, potentially revealing observations that might otherwise go unnoticed or undiscovered. Overall, their benefit is constrained by their reduced photoluminescence intensity and suitability only for dark environments. Project 2 highlighted the effectiveness of Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) in revealing surface details that traditional photography might miss, particularly in assessing the effects of cleaning methods on metals like silver and copper. The RTI technique proved invaluable in detecting potential etching of base metals during cleaning, although further imaging techniques are needed for comprehensive analysis. Project 5 confirmed the efficacy of Fourier Transform Laser Speckle Imaging (FT-LSI) in monitoring solvent spreading and retention within paintings, providing crucial insights for optimizing varnish removal methods. The study showed that FT-LSI is a promising tool for evaluating solvent dynamics in real-life conservation scenarios, though the impact of paint color on experimental results suggests that additional research is needed to refine its application across diverse painting materials and conditions. The techniques are selected and developed based on their evaluation against green parameters, while ensuring that the results maintain the highest professional standards. Key considerations include high accessibility or ease of easy to build (Projects 1, 2, and 5), low energy consumption (Project 1), reuse of samples (Projects 1 and 5), sample development following green protocols (Project 2), and an emphasis on digital sobriety. Collectively, these projects highlight the need for continued development and application of low-tech techniques to enhance conservation practices and ensure the preservation of cultural heritage.

⁷ The authors thank Yu Yam Wong (MSc student UNIBO) for capturing the solvent-induced dynamics of loaded Evolon® CR and PA 6,6 on her prepared zinc white paints varnished with dammar. We also thank Bas Scheepmaker (MSc student University of Wageningen) for preliminary work using LSI to capture SCC and corrosion on metal surfaces and Guus Verhaar (former Rijksmuseum) for preliminary work using LSI to capture solvent transport in heavily crizzled glass.

7. References

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8. Appendices

Appendix I: Images from the 'off-the-shelf camera' experiment

Sample 1: Panel painting, without UV cutting filter, with standing lamps		
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 82A (violet), 5 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 47 (light blue), 1.6 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 56 (green), 1.6 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 12 (yellow), 1.6 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 21 (red), 1.6 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 25 (dark red), 6 sec.

GoGreen – 101060768

GoGreen – 101060768

Sample 2: Mock up, without UV cutting filter, with handheld lamp		
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no.82A (violet), 13 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 47 (light blue), 4 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 56 (green), 6 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 12 (yellow), 10 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 21 (red), 30 sec.
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 25 (dark red), 30 sec.

GoGreen – 101060768

Samples 3 and 4, zinc white reconstructions, with UV cutting filter, with standing lamps			
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 82A (violet), 20 sec.	
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 47 (light blue), 4 sec.	
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 56 (green), 6 sec.	
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 12 (yellow), 4 sec.	
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 21 (red), 4 sec.	
No filter, 1 sec.		Filter no. 25 (dark red), 20 sec.	

GoGreen – 101060768

Samples 5 and 6, burnt sienna reconstructions, with UV cutting filter, with standing lamps		
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 82A (violet), 62.8 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 47 (light blue), 10 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 56 (green), 15 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 12 (yellow), 10 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 21 (red), 20 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 25 (dark red), 56.4 sec.

GoGreen – 101060768

Samples 7, mock-up 2 with varnishes, without UV cutting filter, with handheld lamp, with SONY ILCE 7CM2 camera		
No filter, 0.62 sec.		Filter no.82A (violet), 2.5 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 47 (light blue), 0.5 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 56 (green), 1.6 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 12 (yellow), 1.3 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 21 (red), 1.6 sec.
No filter, 6 sec.		Filter no. 25 (dark red), 10 sec.

Appendix II: Qualitative observations from the imaging and ‘viewing with the eye’ experiments

Qualitative observations of the acquired images and notes from viewing with the eye. All comparisons are between an image using a specific color filter and the image taken without a filter.

Sample 1: Panel painting, standing UV lamps		
Filter	Contrast: between areas where varnish present and where not	Additional information gained
Violet	Reduced; barely readable	None; barely readable
Light blue	Enhanced in comparison to without filter	None
Green	Same as without filter	None
Yellow	Same as without filter	Yes; The red color in one of the cleaned patches stands out more (Section 2.5, Figure 6)
Red	Reduced in comparison to without filter	None
Dark red	Reduced in comparison to without filter	Damages or irregularities in the skin tones stand out more (Section 2.5, Figure 6)
Discrepancies from viewing with the eye: None		
Sample 2: Mock-up with varied varnishes on synthetic paint, standing UV lamps		
Filter	Contrast: between areas where varnish is present and where not	Additional information gained
Violet	Reduced in comparison to without filter	None
Light blue	Reduced in comparison to without filter	None
Green	Same as without filter	Brush strokes on the blue strip of paint is more defined (Section 2.5, Figure 7)
Yellow	Enhanced in comparison to without filter	Differences in intensity between varnishes are clearer (Section 2.5, Figure 8)
Red	Enhanced in comparison to without filter	None
Dark red*	Reduced in comparison to without filter; barely readable	None; barely readable
Discrepancies from viewing with the eye: With the green and yellow filters, it was possible to see the faint fluorescence of some of the varnishes that were applied on the black strip of paint, which was not visible in any of the photos.		
Sample 3 and 4: Zinc white reconstructions, standing lamps		
Filter	Contrast: between areas where dammar or Laropal A81	Additional information gained

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	varnishes were removed	
Violet*	Reduced in comparison to without filter	Confirms a patch of bluish fluorescence seen in the Laropal A81 varnish
Light blue	Enhanced in comparison to without filter	The patch of bluish fluorescence is clearer
Green	Same as without filter	Heterogeneity of the Laropal A81 varnish on the right panel is more visible
Yellow	Same as without filter	Heterogeneity of the Laropal A81 varnish on the right panel is more visible, marks on the left edge of panel more noticeable
Red	Reduced in comparison to without filter	None
Dark red	Reduced in comparison to without filter	None
Discrepancies from viewing with the eye: For the zinc white in egg tempera reconstruction, it was felt that the yellow filter helped with locating some of the varnish removal tests in Laropal A81 varnished areas.		
Sample 5: Burnt sienna reconstructions, standing lamps		
Filter	Contrast: between areas where dammar or Laropal A81 varnishes were removed	Additional information gained
Violet*	Reduced in comparison to without filter; barely readable	None; barely readable
Light blue	Same as without filter	None
Green	Same as without filter	None
Yellow	Same as without filter	None
Red**	Same as without filter	None
Dark red*	Reduced in comparison to without filter; barely readable	None
Discrepancies from viewing with the eye: None		
Sample 7: Mock-up 2, with SONY camera, Jaxman handheld UV lamp		
Filter	Contrast: between areas where varnish is present and where not	Additional information gained
Violet	Reduced in comparison to without filter	None
Light blue	Same as without filter	None
Green	Enhanced in comparison to without filter	None

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Yellow	Enhanced in comparison to without filter	Brushstrokes in the varnish or heterogeneity within each varnish were first noticed when seeing this image (Section 2.5, Figure 9)
Red	Enhanced in comparison to without filter	None
Dark red*	Reduced in comparison to without filter	None
Discrepancies from viewing with the eye:		

*- *deemed too dark for human vision.*

**- *too dark for the right (Burnt sienna in egg tempera) reconstruction.*

Appendix III: Technical details of the experiment

Transmission spectra of filters used

Transmission spectra of filters used, as provided by the supplier, Omegon. The filters are #47 (violet), #82A (light blue), #56 (green), #12 (yellow), #21 (red), and #25 (dark red).

Jaxman handheld UV lamp and ZERO 200/2 UV lamp

Jaxman handheld UV lamp

JAXMAN U1C UV Ultraviolet Light, Nichia Chemicals 6W Ultraviolet 365nm UV LED Flashlight, 18650 Battery, Wide/Flat Beam UV Light, For Resin, Black Light (Batteries Not Included).

Veight : 122g/4.3oz (batteryincluded)

ZERO 200/2 UV lamp

The ZERO 200/2 UV (IP65) lamp is supplied by Helling, Germany. The UV source is 2x9 UV LED. UV intensity at a distance of 400 mm is approximately 5,800 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$. The wavelength of emission is 365 nm, with an emission half-width of approximately 9.0 nm \pm 1 nm.

Appendix IV: Technical analysis of Sample 1

Summary of results

Mercury and calcium were detected in the red robe, along with lead. Therefore, the pigment used there could be any type of red lake, vermillion and red lead, although the lead signal is likely from the ground layer. The skin tone indicated lead and the same red pigments. Starch was also detected in many parts of the painting, indicating a previous consolidation treatment. See below for results and technical details of the pyrolysis GC-MS analysis and handheld X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy analysis conducted by Saskia Smulders (Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands) and Frederik Vanmeert (Rijksmuseum), respectively.

Handheld XRF

XRF analyses were carried out with an Olympus DELTA Professional (currently Evident, Tokyo, Japan). This handheld XRF analyser is equipped with a 4 W Rh-tube (max. 40 kV, max. 200 μ A) and has a changeable collimator size of 3 or 10 mm diameter. XRF is collected using a large area (10 mm²) SDD detector with an energy resolution \leq 145 eV. Each analysis point was probed using two consecutive measurements in air. The first was performed using a voltage of 40 kV, a current of 100 μ A, and 30 s acquisition time for the detection of heavy elements and the second with a voltage of 10 kV, a current of 200 μ A, and 30 s acquisition time for the detection of light elements. Spectral evaluation was performed using the PyMCA software package. The analysis was conducted by Frederik Vanmeert (Rijksmuseum).

Figure 37. Overview of locations where measurements were taken.

Table 9. Overview of elements detected with handheld XRF and possible pigments.

Spot #	Elements detected at High E	Elements detected at Low E	Color of analysed spot	Possible pigments based on XRF results	Other notes
2	Pb, Ca , Fe, Cu, Zn, Sr	Ca , Fe, Pb, S	White	Chalk, lead white, gypsum	S is unclear in this spot because of high Pb
3	Ca, Fe, Cu , Zn, Hg, Pb , Sr	K, Ca , Fe, Pb	Green	Verdigris, malachite, copper acetate	
4	Ca , Fe, Cu, Zn, Pb , Sr	Ca , Fe, Pb, S	Brown	Ochres, van Dyck brown, Kassel earth	
5	Ca, Fe, Cu, Hg, Pb , Sr	Ca , Fe, Pb, S	White	Chalk, lead white, gypsum	
6	Ca, Fe, Cu, Hg , Pb	K, Ca, Fe, Pb	Skin tone	Vermillion, red lead, red ochre, red lake (cochineal lake, brazilwood, madder	S is unclear in this spot because of high Pb

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				lake), lead white	
7	Ca, Fe, Cu, Hg , Pb	K, Ca, Fe, Pb	Red	Vermillion, red lead, red ochre, red lake (cochineal lake, brazilwood, madder lake)	S is unclear in this spot because of high Pb
10	Ca, Fe, Cu , Hg , Pb	K, Ca, Fe, Pb	Red	Vermillion, red lead, red ochre, red lake (cochineal lake, brazilwood, madder lake)	S is unclear in this spot because of high Pb
11	Ca, Mn, Fe , Cu , Hg , Pb , Sr	K, Ca, Fe, Cu, Pb, (Ti)	Black	Bone black, lamp black, carbon black, ivory black, earth pigments	S is unclear in this spot because of high Pb
13	Ca, Mn, Fe , Cu , Hg , Pb , Sr	K, Ca, Mn, Fe , Pb	Black	Bone black, lamp black, carbon black, ivory black, earth pigments	S is unclear in this spot because of high Pb
15	Ca, Fe, Cu , Zn, Hg , Pb , Sr	K, Ca, Fe , Cu, Pb	Green	Verdigris, malachite, copper acetate	S is unclear in this spot because of high Pb

Bold where signal is relatively more intense than other spots

For spots 6, 7, 10: both red lead and lead white are possible. Based on these XRF results it is not possible to make the distinction between both pigments. (However, since lead is found everywhere, I would assume it more likely to be from lead white.)

Pyrolysis GC-MS

Instrumentation

A Frontier Lab 3030D pyrolyzer was used in combination with a Thermo Scientific Trace 1610 gas chromatograph and a Thermo Scientific ISQ7600 mass spectrometer. The pyrolysis technique used was a rapidly rising temperature range from 350°C to 700°C; the temperature of the pyrolysis interface was 290°C. The pyrolysis unit is directly linked to a SLB5 ms Supelco column (with a length of 20m, an internal diameter of 0.18 mm and a film thickness of 0.18 microns) by a split connector. Helium with a programmed flow (0,5 to 1,2 ml/min) is used as carrier gas in combination with a temperature program of 35°C (1) – 60°C/min – 110°C – 14°C/min – 240°C – 5°C/min – 315°C (2). The column is directly coupled to the ion source of the mass spectrometer. The temperature of the interface was 270°C, the temperature of the ion source 220°C. Mass spectra were recorded from 29 to 600 AMU at a speed of 7 scans per second. Xcalibur software 4.6 was used for recording and processing the spectral data.

For the processing of the analysis data, AMDIS software (Automated Mass Spectral Deconvolution and Identification System), developed by NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology, USA) is used. The Py-GC-MS analysis was conducted by Saskia Smulders (Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands).

Figure 38. Overview of locations where scrapings for Py-GC-MS were taken.

GC-MS Results

Table 10. Table of overview of Py-GC-MS results.

Sample	Result of analysis
Sample B	Mostly oil (presumably linseed oil), with some pine resin, with some starch.
Sample C	Mostly oil, (presumably linseed oil with small percentages of brassica oil), with some pine resin, with some starch.
Sample D	Mostly oil, (presumably linseed oil with small percentages of brassica oil), with some pine resin, and remarkable amounts of sulfuric acid from unknown source.
Sample E	Traces of oil, with some pine resin, remarkable amount of sulfuric acid, and synthetic resin.
Sample F	Mostly oil, (presumably linseed oil with small percentages of brassica oil), with some pine resin, and remarkable amounts of sulfuric acid from unknown source, with some starch.

Appendix V: fluorescence spectra of various varnishes

Measurement of fluorescence spectra of various varnishes

Fluorescence spectra of 12 different varnishes were measured using a fluorescence spectrometer (SPEX Fluorolog 3-22 fluorimeter, Horiba) to analyze their optical properties. Each varnish sample was applied on glass slides with a brush. The spectrometer was configured to excite the varnishes at 365 nm, and the resulting fluorescence emissions were recorded from 390 to 700 nm. The image of the glass slides is seen in Figure 39. For the fluorescence spectroscopy varnishes were applied on glass slides, the compositions can be found in Table 11. The varnishes were in solution and collected from the Rijksmuseum, the University of Amsterdam and Frans Hals Museum. They were applied in August 2024 4 days before analysis of the fluorescence spectra. One layer was applied with a brush and left to cure in room temperature.

Figure 39. Image of the glass slides.

Results

The fluorescence spectra of the various tested varnishes overlapped in their peaks and were very similar in intensity. The outlier in fluorescence intensity was the 50% (w/v) Paraloid B72 in acetone varnish sample. As its concentration is much higher than that of other samples including other Paraloid varnish samples, the intensity difference is probably explained by the sheer amount of resin. Its thickness was measured to be 7 micrometers with a thickness gauge measuring between 0-25 mm, with a resolution of 0.001 mm (Helios Preisser). The thickness of other varnishes was not measured. Images of the glass slides were captured, but the fluorescence was too weak to be visible, even with longer exposure times.

Table 11. Varnishes applied on the glass slides.

Sample label	Varnish description (provenance, percentage resin w/v, name of resin, year)
A	FHM 50% Paraloid, 2017
B	FHM 20% Paraloid, 2017
C	FHM 20% Paraloid, 1999, not as yellow
D	UvA 10% Paraloid, 2023
E	FHM unknown % Regalrez, 2019?
F	UvA 15% Regalrez, 2021
G	UvA 20% Regalrez, 2023 with UV blocker Tinuvin and kraton rubber
H	UvA 20% Regalrez, 2023 with UV blocker Tinuvin
I	UvA 20% Laropal A81, 2023
J	FHM 20% Laropal A81, 2019
K	GoGreen 20% Dammar, 2024
M	FHM unknown % MS2A, 2017

Results of fluorescence spectra measurements

Figure 40. Fluorescence spectra of dammar, Laropal A81, and MS2A varnishes.

Figure 41. Fluorescence spectra of Paraloid B72 varnishes.

Figure 42. Fluorescence spectra of Regalrez 1094 varnishes.

Appendix VI: Software NanoMoi

Camera set-up

Camera setup / AlignCameras / Varnish removal / Salt crystalliz. / Spectrogram

Experiment name

Color camera performance (Target)			Speckle camera performance (Target)		
FPS:	2.5	(5.0)	FPS:	10.0	(10.0)
Focus:	1.0	(maximize)	Focus:	0.0	(maximize)
Underexposure:	91.77	(<1%)	Underexposure:	99.98	(<1%)
Overexposure:	0.0	(<1%)	Overexposure:	0.0	(<1%)
Lighting:	0	(60-150)	Lighting:	0	(60-150)

Varnish removal tab

Appendix VII: Tissue cleaning using LSI

A. Experimental parameters

Saving one image every 4.0 seconds for 30 minutes.
Brightfield camera: 'AlviumCam_C'
"expT": 38000.0,
"buffer": 10,
"frame_rate": 25.0,
"gain": 18.0
Speckle camera: 'AlviumCam_M'
"expT": 13000.0,
"buffer": 200,
"frame_rate": 10.0,
"gain": 15.0
Protocol name: 'Varnish removal'
"Widgets": ["Liveview_color_withROI", "Liveview_FTLSI", "Graph_TimeTrace", "Cmap_box" "FTLSI length": 128, "Frequency": 2, "Min intensity": 0.0, "Max intensity": 256.0, "X ROI": [88, 358] "Y ROI": [220, 530] "Averaging": 16, "Scaling min": -0.3, "Scaling max": 30.1, "Plus intensity": 0.0, "Zero images": 20, "Filter size": 5, "Save interval": 4.0, "Save length": 30, "Save unit": "minutes", "Save speckle images": true, "Save live images": false, "Save live images with ROI": true, "Save ISI images": true, "Save ISI images raw": true, "Save colormap": true, "Save timetrace": true, "Save timetrace raw": true, "Save spectrum": false, "Save spectrum raw": false, "Save spectrogram": false, "Save spectrogram raw": false

B. Time traces

B1. Cleaning using Evolon® CR

B2. Cleaning using PA 6,6

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C1. Frequency imaging during application of tissue

C1A. Application of Evolon CR®

Evolon, acetone, t = 60 s

Evolon, ethanol, t = 60 s

Evolon, GVL, t = 60 s

Evolon, DMC, t = 60 s

C1B. Application of PA 6,6

PA 6,6, Acetone, t = 60 s

PA 6,6, DMC, t = 60 s

PA 6,6, Ethanol, t = 60 s

PA 6,6, GVL, t = 60 s

C2. Frequency imaging after varnish removal

C2A. Application of Evolon® CR

Evolon, acetone, t = 60 s

Evolon, DMC, t = 60 s

Evolon, ethanol, t = 60 s

Evolon, GVL, t = 60 s

C2B. Application of PA 6,6

PA 6,6, Acetone, t = 60 s

PA 6,6, DMC, t = 60 s

PA 6,6, Etanol, t = 60 s

PA 6,6, GVL, t = 60 s

